

BAHIR DAR UNIVERSITY

BAHIR DAR INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY

FACULTY OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER

ENGINEERING

**SIZING AND PLACEMENT OF DISTRIBUTED GENERATION IN
DISTRIBUTION SYSTEMS FOR VOLTAGE IMPROVEMENT AND POWER
LOSS REDUCTION**

(CASE STUDY MEKELLE POWER DISTRIBUTION)

By

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Advisor

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Bahir Dar, Ethiopia

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A thesis submitted to Bahir Dar Institute of Technology in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Masters of Science in the Electrical Engineering (With Specialization in Power System Engineering).

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DECLARATION

I, the undersigned, declare that this thesis is my original work, and the thesis work has not been presented anywhere for the award of any academic degree, diploma, or certificate, and all source materials used for this thesis have been properly acknowledged.

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This thesis has been submitted for examination with my approval as university advisor.

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Place: Bahir Dar, Ethiopia

Dedicated
To
My family

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ABSTRACT

Most of the electrical power of Ethiopian cities has fed by a radial distribution system. Mekelle is one of the cities supplied by radial network. The case study in this thesis is applied in Mekelle power distribution lines specifically in feeder line KO5. The feeder line is modelled as a single network that has 112 nodes and 64 loads. It has a total capacity of 10.5 MW. The voltage profiles of most of the buses in feeder line are not in the acceptable voltage level (i.e. 0.95-1.05 pu interval). Moreover, the active and reactive power losses of the feeder are 1498.7637kW and 1481.461 kVAr respectively. Therefore, voltage profile improvement and power loss reduction improvement have needed to this problem. Distributed generations are selected as the best solution. A novel method-loss sensitivity based Newton Raphson-Genetic algorithm approach have implemented for sizing and placement of the DG. This method places one DG at a time on a high loss sensitive bus. After that, it calculates the size of the DG corresponding to that bus. For the next DGs, same practice continues until the specified stopping criterion has reached. In this thesis, for comparison purpose load flow analysis for different scenarios has done. It has been studied the impact that distributed generation has on the system. The scenarios have considered based on the type of DGs. PQ and PV type DGs have considered. The ratings of the PQ type and PV types DGs are tested according to the genetic algorithm best fitness function. Thus, single PQ type DG has selected as the best solution to optimize the system. As a result the total active power loss recorded in feeder has minimized to 145.1 kW and the total reactive power loss has minimized to 142 kVAr . In the same way all the weak voltage profiles have also optimized to the standard $\pm 5\%$ voltage deviation level.

Keywords: Distributed generation, DG size, DG location, losses, voltage profile

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND SYMBOLS

AI	Artificial intelligent
CVD	Cumulative voltage deviation
DG	Distributed generation
DLF	Decoupled Load Flow
EEP	Ethiopian Electric power
ETAP	Electrical Transient Analyzer Program
FDLF	Fast Decoupled Load Flow
FF	Fitness function
GA	Genetic alorism
GS	Gauss Siedel Load Flow Method
GWh	Giga watt hour
I	Current flowing through branch
IA	Improved analytical
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineering
IPSO	Improved Particle swarm optimization
J	Jaccobian matrix
KV	Kilo Volt
KVA	Kilo Volt Ampere
kVAr	Amount of reactive power
LSF	Loss Sensitivity Factor
MATLAB	Matrix Laboratory
MVA	Mega Volt Ampere
MVAR	Reactive Power in Mega watts
MW	Real power in Mega Watts
N	Number of nodes
NR	Newton Raphson Method
P.U	Per Unit
PFD	Power factor of single load

PFDG	Power factor of single distributed generation
PL	Total real power loss
PQ	Load Bus
PSAT	Power System Analysis Toolbox
PSO	Particle swarm optimization
PV	Voltage Controlled Bus
Q_i	Reactive power load of i^{th} node
P_i	Active power injections i^{th} node
QL	Total reactive power loss
R	Resistance of the branch
V_i	Voltage at i^{th} bus
VLI	Voltage Limitation Index
W_p	Weight of real power loss
W_q	Weight of reactive power loss
W_v	Weight of Cumulative voltage deviation
X	Reactance of the branch
Y	Admittance of the branch
Z	Impedance of the branch

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Motivation and Background

The power loss and weak voltage profile problems in radial distribution system have motivated the researcher to integrate a distribution generation (DG) to the system. Moreover, improvements in DGs have prepared it viable and smart choice for the perfection[1].

Distribution systems must deliver electricity to each customer's service entrance at an appropriate voltage rating. Different studies have indicated that approximately 13% of the total power generated is consumed as real power losses at the distribution level. Such non-negligible losses have a direct impact on the financial issues and overall efficiency of distribution utilities. Traditionally, distribution power losses are minimized through proper dispatch of reactive power control devices, which can be done by deploying automatic voltage regulators (tap changing transformers) and shunt capacitors installed at low voltage buses[2].

Now days, penetration of DG into distribution systems has been growing around the world. For example, in the United States, demand growth combined with plant retirements is projected to require as much as 1.7 million GWh of additional electrical energy by 2020, almost twice the growth of the last twenty years.[3]. The distribution generators are not connected simply and thus, the sizing and placement of DG should be carefully addressed. Thus, should be installed according to the optimization needed. Here power loss minimization and voltage profile improvement are considered to be optimized. Investigating this optimization problem is the major motivation of this thesis research.[4]

The case study has carried out in feeder line KO5. Feeder line KO5 is one of the feeder lines that fed Mekelle city. There are many reasons for a customer to install a DG. DGs can be less costly as it eliminates the need for expensive construction of distribution and transmission lines. DGs can provide cost effective, environmental friendly, high power quality and more reliable energy solutions than conventional generation [6]. Many analytical methods are presented for the optimal placement and sizing of the DGs [7-9]. In addition to those methods, different artificial intelligent and hybrid methods have also discussed in [1], [4], [10-13].

1.2. Statements of the problem

The electrical energy has usually supplied through transmission and distribution network, which are operating on maximum allowable limits. Extra growth in load causes to reduce the voltage profile and increase the power losses [10]. Electric power providers have a duty to ensure supplying the required voltage level to their customers. The level of voltage and reliability of power supply at the extreme end of the feeders at the case study area of this research-Mekelle distribution system significantly low. The researcher has confirmed that there are many areas serving at a voltage level of below the standard voltage deviation (i.e. 0.95-1.05). Moreover, this weak voltage profile leads the system to high power loss. As a result, a voltage that is not at its limit causes voltage instability and blackout. At certain loading, the voltage drop is not maintained, and it caused weak voltage profile. So, to improve the voltage profile, and to minimize the power loss, a scientific solution is highly required. Thus, the researcher has decided to install DGs to the feeder line. Incorporating distributed generation in it has numerous benefits. Among these loss minimization, cost saving, voltage support, green power, load balancing and reliability of system are some of the benefits [12].

1.3. Objectives of the thesis

1.3.1. General Objective

The main goal of this thesis is to integrate DGs to the power distribution network to decrease the power loss and to improve the voltage profile of the power system.

1.3.2. Specific Objectives

- To analyses the voltage profile and power loss of the system.
- To identify the candidate nodes for the placement of distributed generators based on power loss and voltage profile problems.
- To size the distributed generators for total power loss reduction and voltage profile improvement
- To compare the power loss and voltage profile results after and before the placement of DGs.

1.4. Methodology

Recently updated data have collected from Ethiopian Electric Power Corporation concerned offices .The data are all about distribution networks history, transformer ratings, loads and others related equipments. The aforementioned collected data have analyzed and organized to make suitable for modeling and power flow analysis. After power flow analysis, voltage profile and the amount of lost power is determined. Then a solution has provided for the power loss and weak voltage profiles problems. This thesis work has proposed a solution for the allocation and sizing of Distributed generation (DG) units to reduce real power losses and hence improve voltage profile in KO5 feeder line-Mekelle distribution lines. Newton-Raphson method under load flow study has used to find out the power losses and the voltage profiles of the feeder line. This section presents the methods used to solve the above problems. Both power flow and the optimization methods are used. The program for the optimization system has implemented in Matlab 2013a software.

To solve the optimization problem, this thesis has developed two stage methods. In the first stage, loss sensitivity analysis (LSF) is employed to select the most appropriate candidate buses for the DG unit's placement's. The second stage, a genetic algorithm has implemented to find the optimal sizing of DGs. applying these methods together with Newton Raphson power flow method the optimization problem is solved.

1.5. Scope of the thesis

The thesis is limited on the investigation of DG impacts on losses and voltage profile only. The scope of this thesis is the study of the steady state analysis of a power system considering voltage and power losses .Issues related with protection of power systems have not considered in this thesis. The scope and limitation of the study are as follow:

- Analyzing of the real power loss and voltage profile
- The allocation and size of the DGs are considering only the power loss and voltage profiles.

1.6. Significant of the Thesis

This thesis might use as a reference and may provide foundation for further research on similar areas of study by other researchers. Finally, the results of this thesis serve as a base for distribution generator planners and designers and give an idea about the distribution generation. Hence, the findings and recommendations will invite governmental and non-governmental organizations and investors to employ their energy and capital in the area.

1.7. Outline of the Thesis

This thesis organized into six chapters.

In **Chapter 1**, introductions and the problems observed on distribution feeders have stated clearly. In addition to this the overall objectives, scopes and the methods used for achieving the main objective have shortly summarized.

Chapter 2, gives a short summary of extensive literature reviews.

Chapter 3, general theoretical backgrounds has discussed. It discusses about distribution system losses, power flow, distributed generations, and optimization algorithms.

In **Chapter 4**, system modeling, power flow study and optimization techniques on power system have analyzed.

In **Chapter 5**, result and discussion have discussed.

Finally, **Chapter 6** concludes the work done and results obtained. Recommendations for future work have also presented.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURES REVIEW

Feeder reconfiguration, transformer reallocation, and connection of autonomous power sources at optimal sizing and locations along radial distribution feeders have formerly carried out with shunt power capacitors. Different methods have established and smeared using different modeling and optimization techniques. The optimization functions specially directed to minimization of power losses increasing of installed capacity control of power factor and improvement of voltage profile[13],[14],[15],[16],[17],[18]. Many researchers have suggested different techniques to answer the problem of voltage improvement and loss minimization in distribution systems. In recent times, researchers are moving away from the usual use of capacitors and all the aforementioned methods to the introduction of DGs in the systems. In the recent past, plentiful energy has contributed to solving the optimal DG placement and sizing problem, utilizing different algorithms, and considering different objectives.

Recent researchers have discovered that installation of Distributed Generators (DGs) in the power network has some advantages which include the improvement in voltage profile [20] and reduction in the power loss on the power network [19],[21],[22],[23]. The degree to which DGs decrease power system loss and improves voltage profile depends on the size and location of the DGs [24],[25]. The different modes through which DGs affect the reactive power in a network enable it to provide voltage support [26]. This support however depends on the deliberate placement and sizing of DG to improve the voltage profile of the network [27]. Hence, to maximize these benefits, it is crucial to find the optimal size of DGs and their appropriate locations in the network, as sitting of DG units in improper locations could jeopardizes the system operation[28]. Various algorithms have developed to solve this problem. Here are some reviews about the past works.

M.Padma Lalitha, V.C. and et al. (2010) proposes a two-stage methodology for an optimal DG placement in the radial distribution systems to reduce the real power losses and to improve the voltage profile. Single DG placement method used to find the optimal DG locations and PSO has used to find the size of the DGs corresponding to maximum loss

reduction. It installs DGs at all the potential locations. However, the literature did not consider different type of DGs [29].

Naveen Jain, S.N. Singh and S.C. Srivastava (2010) presented a method for optimal placement and sizing of multiple DGs using PSO by minimizing power loss while maintaining the voltage profile and stability margin. This method has better improvements over the analytical and old methods [30]. However, in the allocation of multi Distribution Generation it disturbed some of the constraints.

Duong Quoc Hung and Nadarajah Mithulananthan (2013) introduces improved analytical (IA) method for multiple DG allocation for loss reduction in large-scale distribution systems. It uses a method based on IA expressions for finding the size of four different DG types and an effective methodology to find the best location for DG allocation. But the literature didn't include voltage profile improvement [31].

Bhumkittipich, K. and W. Phuangpornpitak, (2013) single DG placement is used to find the optimal DG location and its size which corresponding to the maximum loss reduction. Particle swarm optimization technique has used to determine the optimal location and sizing of that single DG [32].

Analytical approaches have presented in (Naser M. Tabatabaei, Nejat M. and et al. (2014). The proposed method has efficiently examined in DIGSILENT power factory software. It determines the optimal location for placing DG in networked systems to minimize power losses. The proposed approaches are not iterative algorithms, like power flow programs. Therefore, there is no convergence problems involved, and results could be obtained very quickly. However, a series of simulation studies were conducted to verify the validity of the proposed approaches sites to place DGs [33].

Bamigbola, M. Ali and et al. (2014) did traditional optimization method. The traditional optimization method has employed on the minimization of power losses on transmission lines, thus giving a solution, which on implementation is sure to yield the optimal operating scheme. Mathematical model is used for determining of the power losses [34].

Imari, Bahrami S and et al. (2014) the optimal sizing of a small isolated power system that contains renewable and/or conventional energy technologies was determined to minimize the system's energy cost [35].

Ghani, Mohd Ruddin, et al. (2015) proposed Genetic Algorithm (GA) to solve the DG placement and sizing. The result illustrates the losses minimization and the voltage profile improvement. Thus, using DG units in distribution networks is the proper solution in improving the network operation, if the size and placement of units allocated effectively. This literature didn't consider the power factor of the DGs [36].

S Vidyasagar, K Vijayakumar and et al. (2015) discusses about the location and size of DG based on Voltage Limitation Index (VLI). This index has used to ensure that all the buses in the network have acceptable voltage profile according to the distribution permissible limits. After determining the DG size and location a comprehensive analysis on cost of DG, energy loss occurred and savings obtained in the network were listed [37].

Charles, Julius Kilonzi(2016) proposed a hybrid of GA and IPSO to optimize DG location and size while considering both real and reactive power losses. Both real and reactive power flow, and power loss sensitivity factors utilized in identifying the candidate buses for DG allocation. This literature has the advantage of reduced search space for the algorithm and thus increase its rate of convergence. But, long iteration time was noted and thus more work can be done in trying to reduce this time [38].

Osaloni Oluwafunso Oluwole (2016) has presented Genetic Algorithm and Improved Particle Swarm Optimization (GAIPSO) for optimal placement and sizing of DG for power loss reduction and improvement of voltage profile. GA-IPSO has used to optimize DG location and size while considering both real and reactive power losses. The real and reactive power as well as power loss sensitivity factors has utilized in identifying the candidate buses for DG allocation. However, the Multi-objective function can be improved by taking into consideration other power system parameters like system updating issues [39].

All the above stated research works have their own advantage and disadvantages. However, this thesis work uses a suitable technique for the Distributed generation (DG) units to reduce electric power losses and hence improve voltage profile. The method used in this thesis

improves both active and reactive power minimization and voltage profile improvement. The optimization technique used here, works by updating the system successively and thus they improve the system easily.

P. Mahat N. Acharya, and N. Mithulananthan (2016) LSF method for selection of optimum location is based on the principle of linearization of the original exact loss curve around an initial operating point. The LSFs for all buses in the systems have calculated to arrange them in descending order. The top 20% of buses in the LSF list are selected for iterative placement and sizing of the DGs. For each iteration, the losses have calculated by placing the DGs from zero up to the maximum, which has changed in small steps. The size with least losses is select. However, this approach is time consuming and it does not continuously update the network after allocating the first DG. Nevertheless, here in this thesis, the iterations for finding the optimum locations have removed and only the optimum DG sizes have calculated for respective buses to reduce the computation time, and the system has updated successively.

CHAPTER 3

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

3.1. Distribution system

Distribution systems serve as the link from the distribution substation to the customer. This system provides the safe and reliable transfer of electric energy to various customers throughout the service territory. Typical distribution systems begin as the medium-voltage three-phase circuit, typically about 30–60 KV, and terminate at a lower secondary three- or single-phase voltage typically below 1 KV at the customer's premise, usually at the meter[40].

3.1.1. Power loss in distribution system

We know that there are certain losses that affect the economy of the power system. It is a well-known fact that not all energy supplied to a distribution utility reaches the end consumer. A substantial amount of energy is lost in the distribution system by way of Technical and Non-technical losses. The distribution system accounts for highest technical and non-technical losses in the power sector [41],[42],[43].

3.1.2. Types of power loss

3.1.2.1. Technical Losses

Technical losses in power system caused by the physical properties of the components of the power system. The most obvious example is the power dissipated in transmission lines and transformers due to internal electrical resistance. Technical losses are naturally occurring losses (caused by action internal to the power system) and consist mainly of power dissipation in electrical system component such as transmission lines, power transformers, measurement system, etc. Technical losses are possible to compute and control, provided the power system in question consists of known quantities of loads. Technical losses occur during transmission and distribution and involve substation, transformer, and line related losses. These include resistive losses of the primary feeders, the distribution transformer losses (resistive losses in windings and the core losses), resistive losses in secondary network, resistive losses in service drops and losses in kWh meter. Losses are inherent to the distribution of electricity and cannot be eliminated. Technical losses are due to current flowing in the electrical network and generate the

following types of losses:

- **Copper losses:** those are due to I^2R losses that are inherent in all inductors because of the finite resistance of conductors
- **Dielectric losses :** are losses that result from the heating effect on the dielectric material between conductors
- **Induction and radiation losses:** these losses have produced by the electromagnetic fields surrounding conductors. Technical losses are possible to compute and control, provided the power system in question consists of known quantities of loads.

The following are the causes of technical losses:

- Harmonics distortion
- Improper earthing at consumer end
- Long single phase lines
- Unbalanced loading
- Losses due to overloading and low voltage
- Losses due to poor standard of equipment

3.1.2.2.Non-Technical Losses:

Non-Technical losses, on the other hand, caused by actions external to the power system or caused by loads and condition that the Technical losses computation failed to take into account. Non- Technical losses are more difficult to measure because these losses are often unaccounted for by the system operators and thus have no recorded information. Non-technical losses (NTL), on the other hand, occur as a result of theft, metering inaccuracies and unmetered energy.[44]

3.1.3. Measures for reducing technical losses

- Identification of the weakest areas in the distribution system and improving them.
- Reducing the length of LT lines by relocation of distribution sub stations/installations of additional distribution transformers (DTs).

- Installation of lower capacity distribution transformers at each consumer premises instead of cluster formation and substitution of DTs with those having lowered no load losses such as amorphous core transformers.
- Installation of shunt capacitors for improvement of power factor.
- Installation of DGs for power loss reduction.

3.2. Power flow

There are many solution techniques for load flow calculations. However, an acceptable load flow method should meet the requirements such as high speed and low storage requirements, highly reliable, and accepted versatility and simplicity [25],[29],[30]. Load flow studies use to ensure that electrical power transfer from generators to consumers through the grid system is stable, reliable, and economic. Conventional techniques for solving the load flow problem are iterative using the Gauss-Seidel methods Load flow analysis forms an essential prerequisite for power system studies.

3.2.1. Bus classification

A bus is a node at which one or many lines, one or many loads and generators are connected. In a power system each node or bus is associated with 4 quantities, such as magnitude of voltage, phase angle of voltage, active or true power and reactive power in load flow problem two out of these 4 quantities are specified and remaining 2 are required to be determined through the solution of equation. Depending on the quantities that have been specified, the buses are classified into 3 categories.

- **Load bus:** No generator is connected to the bus. At this bus the real and reactive power are specified. It is desired to find out the voltage magnitude and phase angle through load flow solutions. It is required to specify only active power load (P_d) and reactive power load (Q_d) at such bus as at a load bus voltage can be allowed to vary within the permissible values.
- **Generator bus or voltage controlled bus:** Here the voltage magnitude corresponding to the generator voltage and real power (P_g) corresponds to its rating are specified. It is required to find out the reactive power generation (Q_g) and phase angle of the bus voltage.

- **Slack (swing) bus:** For the Slack Bus, it is assumed that the voltage magnitude $|V|$ and voltage phase θ are known, whereas real and reactive powers P_g and Q_g are obtained through the load flow solution

3.3. Newton Raphson Method

Newton-Raphson method is a very powerful load flow solution technique that incorporates first-derivative information when computing voltage updates. Normally, only 3 to 5 iterations are required to solve the load flow problem, regardless of system size. Newton-Raphson is the most commonly used load flow solution technique. The load flow program solves for the set of unknowns that produces power balance at all busses, or as illustrated for bus i in Figure 3.1.

$$P_i^{spec} + jQ_i^{spec} = P_i^{calc} + jQ_i^{calc} \quad (1)$$

$$P_i^{spec} + jQ_i^{spec} = V_i I_i^* \quad (2)$$

$$I_i = I_{B1} + I_{B2} + I_{B3} \quad (3)$$

In other words, the power specified to each bus must equivalent to the power flowing into the system. Note in Figure 3.1 that specified power is drawn as positive generation, to be consistent with KCL equation $YV=I$.

Figure 3.1 Power balance for bus i

Since there are two unknowns at every bus, the size of the load flow problem is $2N$, where N is the number of busses. Obviously, to solve the problem, there must be two equations for every bus. These come from KCL, which for any bus i have the form

$$P_i^{spec} + jQ_i^{spec} = P_i^{calc} + jQ_i^{calc} = V_i I_i^* = V_i \left[\sum_{j=1}^N Y_{ij} V_j \right]^* \quad (4)$$

Separating into real and imaginary components yields two equations for bus i ,

$$P_i^{spec} = \sum_{j=1}^N |V_i| |Y_{ij}| |V_j| \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j - \theta_{ij}) \quad (5)$$

$$Q_i^{spec} = \sum_{j=1}^N |V_i| |Y_{ij}| |V_j| \sin(\delta_i - \delta_j - \theta_{ij}) \quad (6)$$

Where,

$$V_i = |V_i| \angle \delta_i, V_j = |V_j| \angle \delta_j, Y_{ij} = |Y_{ij}| \angle \theta_{ij} \quad (7)$$

In the load flow problem, the matrix update equation is symbolically written in mixed rectangular-polar form as given in equation (8).

$$\begin{aligned} J_1 &= \frac{\partial P}{\partial \delta} & J_2 &= \frac{\partial P}{\partial |V|} \\ J_3 &= \frac{\partial Q}{\partial \delta} & J_4 &= \frac{\partial Q}{\partial |V|} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta P \\ \Delta Q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} J_1 \\ J_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \delta \\ \Delta |V| \end{bmatrix}$$

In highly inductive power systems, P is closely related to voltage angles, and Q is closely related to voltage magnitudes. The above formulation of the Jacobian matrix is often modified to take advantage of symmetry in the partial derivatives. The modification is given in equation (9).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta P \\ \Delta Q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{|V|} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial P}{\partial |V|} \\ \frac{1}{|V|} \frac{\partial Q}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial Q}{\partial |V|} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} |V| \Delta \delta \\ \Delta |V| \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$P_i^{calc} = \sum_{j=1}^N |V_i| |Y_{ij}| |V_j| \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j - \theta_{ij}) \quad (10)$$

$$Q_i^{calc} = \sum_{j=1}^N |V_i| |Y_{ij}| |V_j| \sin(\delta_i - \delta_j - \theta_{ij}) \quad (11)$$

The partial derivatives are derived from equation (10) and (11) and it has the forms given in equations (12-15)

For, J_1

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial P_i}{\partial \delta_i} &= \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N |V_i| |Y_{ij}| |V_j| \sin(\delta_i - \delta_j - \theta_{ij}) \\ \frac{\partial P_i}{\partial \delta_k} &= |V_i| |Y_{ik}| |V_k| \sin(\delta_i - \delta_k - \theta_{ik}) \quad , k \neq i.\end{aligned}\tag{12}$$

For, J_2

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial P_i}{\partial |V_i|} &= \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N |Y_{ij}| |V_j| \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j - \theta_{ij}) + 2|V_i| |Y_{ii}| \cos(\theta_{ii}) \\ \frac{\partial P_i}{\partial |V_k|} &= |V_i| |Y_{ik}| \cos(\delta_i - \delta_k - \theta_{ik}) \quad , k \neq i.\end{aligned}\tag{13}$$

For, J_3

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial \delta_i} &= \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N |V_i| |Y_{ij}| |V_j| \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j - \theta_{ij}) \\ \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial \delta_k} &= |V_i| |Y_{ik}| |V_k| \cos(\delta_i - \delta_k - \theta_{ik}) \quad , k \neq i.\end{aligned}\tag{14}$$

For, J_4

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial |V_i|} &= \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N |Y_{ij}| |V_j| \sin(\delta_i - \delta_j - \theta_{ij}) + 2|V_i| |Y_{ii}| \sin(\theta_{ii}) \\ \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial |V_k|} &= |V_i| |Y_{ik}| \sin(\delta_i - \delta_k - \theta_{ik}) \quad k \neq i.\end{aligned}\tag{15}$$

Note the symmetry in the J terms. If $|V|\delta$ is used as an updating parameter rather than δ , then the expressions for J_1 are

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial P_i}{|V_i| \partial \delta_i} &= \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N |Y_{ij}| |V_j| \sin(\delta_i - \delta_j - \theta_{ij}) \\ \frac{\partial P_i}{|V_k| \partial \delta_k} &= |Y_{ik}| |V_k| \sin(\delta_i - \delta_k - \theta_{ik}), \quad k \neq i.\end{aligned}\tag{16}$$

And, for J_3

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial Q_i}{|V_i| \partial \delta_i} &= \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N |Y_{ij}| |V_j| \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j - \theta_{ij}) \\ \frac{\partial Q_i}{|V_k| \partial \delta_k} &= |Y_{ik}| |V_k| \cos(\delta_i - \delta_k - \theta_{ik}), \quad k \neq i.\end{aligned}\tag{17}$$

The solution procedure for the Newton-Raphson load flow has given in figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2 Flow chart of Newton Raphson Method

3.4. Current and Power Flow in Transmission Lines and Cables

Once the bus voltages throughout the system have been calculated, then the load flow program must calculate power flows through lines/transformers/cables. Since the feeder length is covered a short distance the standard pi-equivalent models are used for this purpose as given in figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3 the standard pi-equivalent models

So, from side j

$$I_{jk} = \frac{|V_j| \angle \delta_j |V_k| \angle \delta_k}{R + jX} + |V_j| \frac{Q}{2} \angle (\delta_j + 90^\circ) \quad (18)$$

And, from side k,

$$I_{kj} = \frac{|V_k| \angle \delta_k |V_j| \angle \delta_j}{R + jX} + |V_k| \frac{Q}{2} \angle (\delta_k + 90^\circ) \quad (19)$$

Note that the current on the two opposite ends of the line are not exactly the same due to the fact that the capacitor currents are not, in general, equal to each other. The power flows for the two ends of the line, directed inward, are

$$S_{jk} = V_{jk} I_{jk}^* \quad , \quad S_{kj} = V_{kj} I_{kj}^* \quad (20)$$

Transmission line values for R, X (or L), and line charging Q (or C), shown on the previous diagram, are entered in per unit for the entire length of the line. The relationship between these parameters and the per-meter calculations developed in the transmission line are discussed in chapter four.

3.5. Distributed Generation

DG can be classified into four major types based on their terminal characteristics in terms of real and reactive power delivering capability as follows:

- 1) Type 1: DG capable of injecting P only.
- 2) Type 2: DG capable of injecting Q only.
- 3) Type 3: DG capable of injecting both P and Q.
- 4) Type 4: DG capable of injecting P but consuming Q.

Photovoltaic, micro turbines, fuel cells, which are integrated to the main grid with the help of converters/inverters, are good examples of Type 1. Type 2 could be synchronous compensators such as gas turbines. DG units that are based on synchronous machine (cogeneration, gas turbine, etc.) fall in Type 3. Type 4 is mainly induction generators that used in wind farms [27], [26]. Distributed Generation is also referred to “Decentralized Generation” in parts of Asia and Europe, “Embedded Generation” across the United States and “Dispersed Generation” in North America. The technology incorporates wind turbines, micro turbines, photovoltaic systems, fuel cells, energy storage, and synchronous generator applications to supply active power to distributed systems connected close to the consumers load. Section 3.5.1 of this paper provides a brief outline of general types of distributed generation technologies and key issues facing integration of the grid [46].

3.5.1. Types of Distributed Generation

3.5.1.1. Photovoltaic

Photovoltaic (PV) technology converts solar energy directly into electricity using semiconductor solar cells. These cells are manufactured in small of usually around one square centimeter. When the solar cells are exposed to direct sunlight, each cell generates less than one watt of DC power, with the lowest voltage around 0.5 V. Normally, a panel or module can be formed by electrically connecting twelve solar cell units in series to provide 12 V. In the same way, a group of modules can be connected together in series and parallel to increase the output to the needed power. PV systems are divided into three sizes based on the power they produce (the small size is less than 10 kW; the medium size is 10 kW to 100 kW; and the large size is

more than 100 kW). The large size is appropriate for the distribution network level .Despite the high initial price of PV systems (US \$6,000-10,000/LW), the most significant features are that no fuel is needs to operate them, and they are very clean and quiet [2].

3.5.1.2. Micro Turbines

Micro turbines are typically defined as systems with an output power rating between 10kW up to a few hundred kilowatts. These systems are usually a single shaft design with compressor, turbine and generator all on the common shaft [45]. Micro-turbines (MT) are small electricity generators that burn fuel such as natural gas, propane, and fuel oil to create high-speed rotation that is transferred to an electrical generator via a main shaft. MT consists of three basic components: a compressor, a turbine generator, and a recuperator. In present energy markets, MT generators are the most improved and most attractive devices in distributed power generation equipment. Their capacity ranges from 20 kW to 500 kW and their efficiency is more than 80% when the CHP application is used in the system. Also, the NOx low compared to large-scale turbines .emissions of MT are very low compared to large-scale turbines [2].

3.5.1.3. Reciprocating Engines

These DG technologies have developed more than a century ago, and are still widely utilized in a broad array of applications. The engines range in size from less than 5 to over 5,000 kW, and use diesel, natural gas, or waste gas as their fuel source. Development efforts remain focused on improving efficiency and on reducing emission levels. Reciprocating engines are being used primarily for backup power, peaking power, and in cogeneration applications [47].

3.5.1.4. Industrial combustion turbines

A mature technology, combustion turbines range from 1 MW to over 5 MW. They have low capital cost, low emission levels, but also usually low electric efficiency ratings. Development efforts are focused on increasing efficiency levels for this widely available technology. Industrial combustion turbines are being used primarily for peaking power and in cogeneration applications [47].

3.5.1.5. Fuel cells

A fuel cell is an electromechanical engine. It harnesses the energy released when hydrogen and oxygen combine. This reaction produces electricity, heat and water. Fuel cells produce almost no pollutants and have no moving parts. In principle, a fuel cell operates like a battery. However, a fuel cell does not run down or require recharging. It will produce energy in the form of electricity and heat as long as fuel is supplied. The hydrogen needed for reaction in a fuel cell is typically produced from hydrogen rich fuels such as natural gas, propane, or methane from biogas recovery. These hydrogen rich fuels are run through a fuel "reformer" that converts the fuel from its original composition to hydrogen and to carbon dioxide.

3.5.1.6. Wind Turbines

Wind power generation harnesses the energy of wind to drive electric power generators. This is achieved using some form of wind turbine which is operated either at variable or constant speed. The advantage of using wind turbines compared to many other devices comes as there is no fuel charge, no pollution, potentially a 24-hour source of energy and units are modular with fairly linear power vs. cost relationship for large-scale installations.

Disadvantages include high initial cost, unpredictability of energy production and greater environmental impacts compared to solar. Horizontal-axis wind turbines have a "yaw control" which is a mechanism to keep them pointed into the wind. This is necessary in order to maintain power production and avoid operating problems such as resonance and vibration. If the wind turbine is designed with the rotor located behind the tower, yaw adjustment will occur automatically as the wind direction shifts. As for rotors located behind the tower they create difficulties of their own including vibration, uneven speed and loss of potential given that blades pass through the wind shadow. On the other hand, vertical-axis wind turbines have several advantages over horizontal axis wind turbines. The majority of their mechanical and electrical machinery is located on the ground rather than 40 - 90 m in the air. This makes maintenance and operation simpler and reduces structural needs. Furthermore, vertical-axis wind turbines do not need a yaw control.

3.5.2. DG impacts and Modeling

DG offers a long list of benefits, which can be, primarily, classified into three broad categories, namely, economical, technical, and environmental advantages. Economic advantages cover saving world fuel, saving transmission and distribution cost and reducing wholesale electricity price. On the other hand, environmental advantages include low noise and low emission. Technical advantages cover a wide variety of issues such as peak load saving, good voltage profile, reduced system losses, improved continuity and reliability, removal of some power quality problems and relaxed thermal constraints of Transmission and Distribution (T&D) feeders. Reducing the total system losses could be of interest to some utilities in the developing countries as some of them are losing 15-20% of their total generation as losses[48].

The main reason of using DG units in power system is technical and economic benefits that have presented as follows. Some of the major technical benefits:

- reduced line losses;
- Voltage profile improvement;
- Reduced emissions of pollutants;
- Increased overall energy efficiency;
- Enhanced system reliability and security;
- Improved power quality;
- Relieved transmission & distribution congestion.

In addition, some of the major economic benefits:

- Deferred investments for upgrades of facilities;
- Reduced operation & maintenance costs of some DG technologies;
- Reduced fuel costs due to increased overall efficiency;
- Reduced reserve requirements and the associated costs;
- Lower operating costs due to peak shaving;
- Increased security for critical loads.

3.5.3. DG Impact on Fault Level and Protection Devices

When the DG connected to the distribution grid changes the fault level. The impact on the fault level depends on the ability of the DG unit to contribute to the fault current. We might

also have back flow in the case fault, i.e.; fault current may also flow from load side to source side. This means that protective devices may see fault currents for a fault in the downstream section and in the upstream section [49]. A significant contribution to the fault current of the DG unit affects the protective devices in the distribution system. Because the fault currents are affected by the DG-units, the measured currents used for protection purposes, are affected as well. This can lead to incorrect operation of the protective system and causes fault detection problems and selectivity problems. There are some protection requirements that are established by the utility company. Adequate interconnection protection should consider both parties ensuring the achievement of the utility requirements. Interconnection protection is usually dependent on size, type of generator, interconnection point and interconnecting transformer connection [50],[51].

3.5.4. Optimal sizing of the DG

The total active power losses of the system is a parabolic function that becomes minimum, if the partial derivatives of the power loss formula, with respect to active power injection from the DG at bus i , tend to zero.

We are considering $a = (sign) \tan (\cos^{-1} (PF_{DG}))$ for optimal positioning of a DG unit in a radial distribution system. The reactive power generated by a DG unit can be expressed by the following equation as[52, 53].

$$Q_{DGi} = a P_{DGi} \quad (21)$$

In which

$sign = +1$: reactive power supplied by a DG.

$sign = -1$: reactive power absorbed by a DG.

PF_{DG} = Power factor of DG

The active power and reactive power injected at bus i by a DG can be given by the following equation

$$P_i = P_{DGi} - P_{di} \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_i &= Q_{DG_i} - Q_{d_i} = aP_{DG_i} - Q_{d_i} \\
P_{loss} &= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \left[a_{ij} (P_i P_j + Q_i Q_j) + b_{ij} (Q_i P_j - P_i Q_j) \right] \quad (23)
\end{aligned}$$

P_i and Q_i are active and reactive power of the bus; P_{D_i} and Q_{D_i} are the loads at bus i . P_{DG_i} and Q_{DG_i} are power injections of DGs to the bus. Using the exact loss formula, the sensitivity of active power losses with respect to active power injection from the DG is given by [54]. From equation (22) and (23) the active power loss which occurred in the distribution system can be computed in the following way

$$P_{loss} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \left[\begin{aligned} & \alpha_{ij} \left[(P_{DG_i} - P_{d_i}) P_j + (aP_{DG_i} - Q_{d_i}) Q_j \right] + \\ & \beta_{ij} \left[(aP_{DG_i} - P_{d_i}) P_j - (P_{DG_i} - P_{d_i}) Q_j \right] \end{aligned} \right] \quad (24)$$

The partial derivative of equation (24) with respect to the active power injection from DG at bus ' i ' becomes zero to obtain reduced active power loss.

$$\frac{\partial P_{loss}}{\partial P_{DG_i}} = 2 \sum_{j=1}^n \left[\alpha_{ij} (P_j + aQ_j) + \beta_{ij} (aP_j - Q_j) \right] = 0 \quad (25)$$

Equation (25) can be written in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \alpha_{ii} (P_i + aQ_i) + \beta_{ii} (aP_i - Q_i) + \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n (\alpha_{ij} P_j - \beta_{ij} Q_j) \\
& + a \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n (\alpha_{ij} Q_j + \beta_{ij} P_j) = 0
\end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Now let

$$\begin{aligned}
X_i &= \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n (\alpha_{ij} P_j - \beta_{ij} Q_j) \\
Y_i &= \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n (\alpha_{ij} Q_j + \beta_{ij} P_j)
\end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

From equations (22), (23), (26) and (27) we can obtain equation (28) stated as below

$$\alpha_{ii}(PDG_i - P_{di} + a^2 P_{DG_i} - aQ_{di}) + \beta_{ii}(Q_{di} - aP_{di}) + X_i + aY_i = 0 \quad (28)$$

Rearranging the above equation, we can obtain equation (29) to get the formulae to compute the best size of a DG to be placed in distribution system to reduce losses

$$P_{DG_i} = \frac{\alpha_{ii}(P_{di} + aQ_{di}) + \beta_{ii}(aP_{di} - Q_{di}) - X_i - aY_i}{a^2\alpha_{ii} + \alpha_{ii}} \quad (29)$$

The power factor of a DG unit is very important to minimize the total system losses and it depends upon the DG type and its operating condition. When the power factor of DG is given, the optimal size of DG at each bus i for minimizing losses can be found in the following way.[53]

Type 1 DG: These types of DG systems produce the real power such as photovoltaic. [55]. This kind of DG is injecting only active power such as fuel cells, photovoltaic system, micro-turbines. Power factor is unity for this type i.e. $PF_{DG} = 1$, $a = 0$. From (29) the optimal size of DG at each bus i for minimizing losses can be given by reduced equation (23).

$$P_{DG_i} = P_{di} - \frac{1}{\alpha_{ii}} \left[\beta_{ii}Q_{di} + \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n (\alpha_{ij}P_j - \beta_{ij}Q_j) \right] \quad (30)$$

Type 2 DG: Assuming $PF_{DG} = 0$ and $a = \infty$, from (29), the optimal size of DG at each bus i for minimizing losses is given by reduced equation (23)

$$Q_{DG_i} = Q_{di} + \frac{1}{\alpha_{ii}} \left[\beta_{ii}P_{di} - \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n (\alpha_{ij}Q_j + \beta_{ij}P_j) \right] \quad (31)$$

Type 3 DG: This kind of DG is generating active power as well as reactive power such as diesel generators. Power factor is in the range $0 < PF_{DG} < 1$, $sign = +1$ and a is a constant. The best size of Type 3 DG for minimum loss can be obtained from the equation (23).

3.5.5. Optimal power factor

The other issue is the optimal power factor of DG units to be placed. To understand the concept of the power factor selection, we can consider a simple distribution system with two buses, a source, a load, and a DG connected through a transmission line as shown in the figure below:

Figure 3.2 A simple distribution system with single DG

PF of the single DG (PF_{DG}) connected to the distribution system can be obtained as,

$$PF_{DG} = \frac{P_{DG}}{\sqrt{P_{DG}^2 + Q_{DG}^2}} \quad (32)$$

PF of a single load can be obtained as,

$$PF_d = \frac{P_d}{\sqrt{P_d^2 + Q_d^2}} \quad (33)$$

When the PF of a single DG is equal to PF of combined load at that time the total load PF can be computed from equation (23) at that calculation the total active and reactive power can be obtained as,

$$P_{di} = \sum_{i=1}^n P_{di} \quad (34)$$

$$Q_{di} = \sum_{i=1}^n Q_{di} \quad (35)$$

It is found that minimum loss will be obtained if the power factor of DG (PF_{DG}) is equal to power factor of total load (PF). This can be expressed by equation (36)

$$PF_{DG} = PF_d \quad (36)$$

3.6. Optimization Technique

Optimization is the process of adjusting the inputs to or characteristics of a device, mathematical process, or experiment to find the minimum or maximum output or result. The input consists of variables; the process or function is known as the cost function, objective function, or fitness function; and the output is the cost or fitness[56].

3.6.1. Genetic Algorithm

Genetic algorithm (GA) is one of the stochastic search algorithms based on the mechanics of natural genetics. A GA allows a population composed of many individuals to evolve under specified selection rules to a state that maximizes the “fitness” (i.e., minimizes the cost function) [56]. The GA begins, like any other optimization algorithm, by defining the optimization variables, the cost function, and the cost. It ends like other optimization algorithms too, by testing for convergence. In between, however, this algorithm is quite different [56]. A solution variable for the problem is first represented using artificial chromosomes (strings). In other words, the problem is encoded to strings that GA can handle. A string represents one search point in the solution space. GA is a parallel search method because it uses set (population) of strings (i.e. multiple search points). It modifies strings (searching points) using natural selection and genetic operators such as crossover and mutation. After convergence, strings are decoded to the original solution variables and the final solutions are obtained [48].

Generally, GA comprises three different phases of search: phase 1: creating an initial population; phase 2: evaluating a fitness function; phase 3: producing a new population. A genetic search starts with a randomly generated initial population within which each individual is evaluated by means of a fitness function. Individual in this and subsequent generations are duplicated or eliminated according to their fitness values. Further generations are created by applying GA operators. This eventually leads to a generation of high performing individuals.

The main advantages of GA over conventional optimization methods are [57]:

- They do not need any prior knowledge, space limitations, or special properties of the objective function about the problem to be optimized.
- They do not deal directly with the parameters of the problem. They only require codes, which represent the parameters and the evaluation of the fitness function to assign a quality value to every solution produced.
- They work with a set of solutions from one generation to the next, making the process likely to converge into a global minimum.

The solutions obtained are randomly based on the probability rate of the genetic operators such as mutation and crossover. This technique is very useful for solving optimization problems, such as the problem solved in this paper [57].

3.6.1.1. Representation

A population is formed by a set of individuals that correspond with a possible solution of the problem. Each individual is represented by a set of the variables to be optimized; they are usually represented in a string form that is called chromosome. The method of chromosome’s representation has a major impact on the performance of the GA. There are two common representation methods for numerical optimization problems:

- a) **Binary string representation method:** - The most important issue is to decide the number of bits used to encode the variables to be optimized;
- b) **Vector of integers and real numbers:** - In this method, each integer or real number represents a single variable. Each element (bit, integer, or real number) in a chromosome is called gene.

In this thesis the individual is represented by a vector with size equal to the number of buses in the system, as shown in Figure 3.3 .The vector is filled in a binary form, where 1 is the point of allocation.

1	2	3	N bus
0	1	0	0

Figure 3.3 Example of encoding or representation of an individual

3.6.1.2. Initial Population

GA requires a group of initial solutions to start the process of optimization instead of a single one. This initial population can be created in two ways. The first one consists of using randomly produced solutions created by a random generator and it is used in those cases in which no prior knowledge existed. The second method employs a set of known solutions that

satisfied the requirements of the problem. This method requires a previous knowledge about the optimization problem and converges to an optimal solution in less time than the first one. The initial population is represented by a matrix initial population by number of buses. The individuals in the population are randomly generated.

3.6.1.3. Fitness Evaluation Function

The formulation of the fitness function (FF) is a very important aspect of the optimization problem. FF assigns a quality value to each individual of the population depending on how well the solution performs the desired functions and satisfied the given constraints. It allows to determinate which individuals of the population survive for the next generation. The fitness values of individuals in a given population are employed to drive the evolution process. In the case of a GA, this calculation must be automatic and the problem is how to devise a procedure that computes the quality of the solution. These characteristics enable the GA to present excellent results even when optimizing complex, multimodal, or discontinuous functions.

3.6.1.4. Genetic operators

After application of fitness function, three basic genetic operators are applied to the population in order to create a new population, such as selection, crossover, and mutation. All of them are inspired by nature but it is not necessary to employ all the operators in a GA. The choice or design of the operators depends on the problem and the representation scheme employed.

Selection: it is a production operator (elitism). The aim of the selection procedure is to copy individuals whose fitness values are higher than those whose fitness values are low in the next generation. Selection makes one or more copies of any individual that possess a high fitness value; otherwise, the individual is eliminated from the solution pool[58].

This operator allows transmitting the best individual's genetic material in the next generations in order to drive the search towards a promising area and finding good solutions in a short time. After the initial population is formed, selection is performed. In this method, two groups of potential parents are generated; each group will consist of k individuals randomly chosen within the current population. In each group the best individual is chosen, which has the best

objective function. At the end of this process, two individuals are selected, named as parents, who are employed in the recombination step [59],[60].

Crossover (Recombination): this operator selects two individuals within the generation and a crossover site and carries out a swapping operation of the string bits to the right-hand side of the crossover site of both individuals. Crossover operations synthesize bits of knowledge gained from both parents exhibiting better than average performance. Thus, the probability of a better offspring is greatly enhanced [58]. The recombination method is the cut at a single point, chosen in random order, as shown in Figure 3.4. After carrying out the recombination, descendants is generated and each one inherits characteristics of both parents. This operator is considered the most important one of GA method because it is responsible for the genetic recombination. It is used to create two new individuals (children) from two existing ones (parents), they are picked from the current population through the selection operator. There are several ways of doing this. Common crossover operations are; one point, two-point, cycle and uniform crossovers. The crossover operation breaks parents' chromosome from one spot and displace the broken parts with each other. As it can be seen in the figure below child chromosomes are born. The possibility of the crossover operation on the parents' chromosome is P_c which is between 0 and 1[61].

Figure 3.4 Crossover operation

Mutation: This operator acts as a background operator and is used to explore some of the invested points in the search space by randomly flipping a 'bit' in a population of strings. In this procedure, all individuals in the population are checked gene by gene and the gene value is randomly reversed according to a specified rate. This operation introduces new information in the algorithm in order to force the algorithm to search new areas. This operator helps GA avoid premature convergence due to genetic material that has been lost during the selection operation. Besides, it helps to find the global optimal solution. According to the mutation rate, individual points are selected at random to change their state, as seen in Figure 3.5

Figure 3.5 Mutation

The proper solutions can be determined by the value, which obtains from the fitness function. In the minimization problem the less value of the fitness function shows the better solution, by the way the problem constraints should be satisfied.

3.6.2. Control parameters

The most important control parameters of a simple GA are:

- **Population size:** It allows a better exploration of the solution space during the search so that the probability of convergence to the global optimal solution is higher.
- **Crossover rate:** It determines the frequency of the crossover operation. It is used to discover a promising area at the start of the simulation.
- **Mutation rate:** It controls the mutation operation. In general, an increase in the mutation rate helps the GA to reach the global solution avoiding the local minimum. However, if this mutation rate parameter is very high, there could be high diversity in the population and the global solution is not reached.

3.6.3. Effect of Parameter

There are three important parameters in the method threshold for rules; population; and number of subsystems. The most sensitive and important factor is threshold. If we assign high value to the threshold (e.g. 0.21, the convergent speed is improved. However, the possibility converging to local solutions becomes higher. If we assign low value to the threshold such as 0.05, the convergent speed becomes slow. However, most of converged solution are close to the global optimal.

The population is also important. The greater the number of population have higher possibility to get a global optimal. The greater population, however, requires the computing time. After a lot of iterations, generations tend to become homogeneous. Even if the population is high, the variety will be lost in such cases. Keeping fresh members in generations is more essential. Although interbreeding is the most important operation in the proposed method, the numbers of subsystems are not sensitive [62].

Figure 3.6 The Basic Genetic Algorithm

The basic Genetic Algorithm Program has given below.

```
{ % Generate random population of chromosomes
```

```
Initialize population;
```

```

Evaluate population; %Fitness
while Termination_Criteria_Not_Satisfied
{
Select parents for reproduction; %Selection
Perform crossover; %Crossover
Perform mutation; %Mutation
Accept new generation;
Evaluate population; %Fitness
}
}

```

Generally the GA algorithm will end when at least one of the conditions is met [63] .

- **Generations** – the algorithm stops when it reaches the specified maximum number of generations.
- **Time** – the algorithm runs for the specified amount of time in seconds.
- **Fitness Limit** – the algorithm stops when the fittest value in the current generation is less than or equal to the specified fitness limit.
- **Stall Generations** – the algorithm stops when there is no improvement in the fitness function value for a certain number of generations.
- **Stall Time Limit** – the algorithm stops when there is no improvement in the fitness function for a certain period in seconds.

CHAPTER 4

DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

In this section, the methodology and case studies used in this thesis for analyzing the system has discussed. Both the power flow technique and the optimization method used in this thesis have programmed in Matlab 2013a.

4.1. Case Study

The thesis has done in feeder line KO5. This feeder line is found in Mekelle distribution systems. Feeder KO5 has 112 nodes and 111 segments. It has 64 loads total capacity of 10.5 MW capacities. All the loads have fed from the substation located at Lachi. The loads belonging to one segment have placed at the end of each segment. The layout diagram of Lachi substation has illustrated in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1 Lachi substation network

The distribution network feeder line KO5 has drawn in Microsoft office Visio2007 as shown in Figure 4.2 This has done for ease of analysis. Low voltage profile buses and points affected by loss can be clearly visualized during analysis. The single arrow

emerging from the nodes are the loads supplied by the transformers. The feeder is radiated from the substation (node number 1). Power flow of the feeder goes from the substation point (node 1) to the branches of the radially distributed network.

Figure 4.2 Network Diagram for Feeder ko5

The current power distribution in Mekelle city is of radial distribution system type. Power is delivered to the customer from the utility in a straightforward fashion. There are no laterals and interconnection or mesh type network topology. Though radial power distribution system is less costly in terms of design and protection, it's vulnerable to disturbance hence less reliable. From all the outgoing feeders, KO5 feeder has

recorded low voltage profile at its different buses.

4.2. System modeling

The modeling of the system done based on the assumption that the three-phase system assumed balanced under steady state conditions. The available locations to install the suggested distributed generators are selected among the nodes with the highest loss sensitivity factor (LSF) in addition to the physical factors and right of way which are considered as important factors affecting this selection. The load flow algorithm identifies the nodes with the highest LSF. The parameters for the load flow are calculated first.

4.2.1. Impedance Calculation of Overhead Line

The inductance of a transmission line depends upon the material, dimensions, and configuration of the wires and length with the spacing between them. AC resistance of a conductor is always higher than its DC resistance due to the skin effect forcing more current flow near the outer surface of the conductor. The higher the frequency of current, the more noticeable skin effect would be. Wire manufacturers usually supply tables of resistance per unit length at common frequencies (50 and 60 Hz). Therefore, the resistance can be determined from such tables. The conductors that are used in distribution feeders are stranded conductors. The inductive reactance is calculated at a frequency of 50Hz, and at a length of one kilometer. Thus, impedances are given by.

$$Z_a = R_a + j0.062832 \ln \frac{D}{GMR_a} \Omega / km \quad (37)$$

$$GMR_a = K.r$$

$$D = \sqrt[3]{D_{ab} \cdot D_{bc} \cdot D_{ac}} \quad (38)$$

Where:

GMR_a = Geometric mean ratio of conductor a.

k = the GMR factor

r = actual conductor radius

Z_a = impedance of conductor a in Ω/km

R_a = resistance of conductor i in Ω/km

D = distance between conductors in meter

D_{ab} =Distance between conductors a and b in meter

D_{bc} =Distance between conductors b and c in meter

D_{ac} =Distance between conductors a and c in meter

Using the data in Table 4.1 and Table 4.1 and applying equations (37) and (38) the following.

1. For AAC-120 conductor type the self-impedance for phase conductors is

$$\begin{aligned}Z_a &= R_a + j0.062832 \ln \frac{D}{GMR_a} \Omega / \text{km} \\Z_a &= 0.3085 + j0.062832 \ln \frac{0.72135}{9.24 * 10^{-3}} \Omega / \text{km} \\&= 0.2853 + j0.2738 \Omega / \text{km}\end{aligned}$$

For the three phases three conductors the impedance of each conductor is the same (*i.e.* $Z_a = Z_b = Z_c$). Then the positive sequence impedance of the conductors is obtained by multiplying the impedance per kilometer by its length.

2. For AAC-95 conductor type the self-impedance for phase conductors is

$$\begin{aligned}Z_a &= R_a + j0.062832 \ln \frac{D}{GMR_a} \Omega / \text{km} \\Z_a &= 0.3085 + j0.062832 \ln \frac{0.72135}{4.129 * 10^{-3}} \Omega / \text{km} \\&= 0.3085 + j0.32441 \Omega / \text{km}\end{aligned}$$

For the three phases three conductors the impedance of each conductor is the same (*i.e.* $Z_a = Z_b = Z_c$). In the same manner with the above method then the positive sequence impedance of the conductors is obtained by multiplying the impedance per

kilometer by its length.

3. For AAC-50 conductor type

Using the same procedure like AAC-95 the process and equations are followed to obtain the impedances of the conductor AAC-50. Thus, the positive sequence impedance

$$\begin{aligned}Z_a &= R_a + j0.062832 \ln \frac{D}{GMR_a} \Omega / km \\Z_a &= 0.5785 + j0.062832 \ln \frac{0.72135}{2.88 * 10^{-3}} \Omega / km \\&= 0.5785 + j0.34702 \Omega / km\end{aligned}$$

For the three phases three conductors the impedance of each conductor is the same. (*i.e.* $Z_a = Z_b = Z_c$). Then the positive sequence impedance of the conductors is obtained by multiplying the impedance per kilometer by its length. Since the line is short, the shunt admittance of overhead lines is neglected.

4. For AAC-25 conductor type

Using the same procedure like AAC-50 the process and equations are followed to obtain the impedances of the conductor AAC-25. Thus, the positive sequence impedance

$$\begin{aligned}Z_a &= R_a + j0.062832 \ln \frac{D}{GMR_a} \Omega / km \\Z_a &= 0.5785 + j0.062832 \ln \frac{0.72135}{1.881 * 10^{-3}} \Omega / km \\Z_a &= 1.181 + j0.37367 \Omega / km\end{aligned}$$

Table 4.1: GMR Factor (k) and Strand Relationship for AAC conductor

Strands	GMR factor, k
1	0.7788
3	0.6778
7	0.7256
19	0.7577
37	0.7678
61	0.7722

Table 4.2: Conductor parameters in the feeder

Conductor type	Nominal area (mm ²)	Actual area (mm ²)	Stranding and wire diameter	Overall diameter (mm)	Actual diameter (mm)	GMR (mm)	Resistance (W/km)
AAC	25	24.2	7/2.1	6.3	5.56	1.88	1.181
AAC	50	49.5	7/3.00	9	7.9377	2.88	0.5785
AAC	95	93.5	19/2.5	12.5	10.8975	4.129	0.3085
AAC	120	117	19/2.8	14	12.2	9.24	0.2853

Table 4.2 discusses about the parameters of the feeder line. All the conductors used are AAC type but different diameters. The GMR for each conductor is also given in table 4.2.

Figure 4.3 presents the model of one electric pole in power distribution systems. The gap distance between the phase lines have stated clearly.

Figure 4.3 Distance between conductors

4.2.2. Load Modeling

Load models usually can be classified into two main categories: static and dynamic. Since power flow analysis is mainly performed for static states of power systems, only static load is considered here in this thesis. Constant power model (constant P and Q), i.e., the load power doesn't vary with the voltage magnitude. This system is modeled as constant power. Constant power loads describe real and reactive power absorbed by the system so that these are modeled as positive power injections at the buses. In order to keep a constant power injection, these loads are characterized by reacting to changes in the voltage or current. The complete data of the feeder line loads are given in Appendix A.

4.3. Power System Analysis

The single line diagram of a power system has shown in the Figure 4.1. The line impedances have also given the appendix A. The step-by-step procedure for matrix formulation is explained as given below.

4.3.1. Algorithm for Zbus Computation

Having formed Ybus and Zloop Zbus and Yloop can be obtained by inversion of the corresponding matrices [34, 50],[51]. This is major inversion, requiring more storage space and time in the digital computer. In order to avoid the major inversion, an algorithm have been developed to form Zbus by adding one line or element at a time and computing the resultant matrix. The size of the matrix is increased by one when a tree branch has added, whereas all the entries of the matrix have modified when a link has added. This method involves inversion of small size matrices whenever an element or line, mutually coupled to the existing elements in the network, has added.

4.3.2. Algorithm for Ybus computation

The matrix Ybus is formed by step-by-step addition of a line. The size of the matrix is increased by one for the addition of a tree branch that adds a new bus, modifying the existing entries of Ybus, whereas the size remains the same for the addition of a link but the entries of the existing matrix are modified.

4.3.4. Addition of Branch p-q

Consider a network with n buses, to which a line p-q has added. This adds a new bus to the network. The line p-q has mutual coupling with some or all of the existing lines or elements in the network.

4.3.5. Algorithm for Load flow computation

The load flow problem consists of the calculation of power flows, and voltages of a network for specified terminal or bus conditions. A single-phase representation is adequate since power systems are usually balanced. Associated with each bus are four quantities: the real and reactive power, the voltage magnitude and the phase angle. Node1 has selected as slack bus, to provide the additional real and reactive power to supply the distribution network losses. At this

bus the voltage magnitude and phase angle have specified. The remaining buses of the system have designated as load buses. The real and reactive powers have specified at a load bus.

While implementing load flow the following assumptions have taken.

- Three phase radial distribution networks were balanced and represented by their single line diagrams.
- Charging capacitances have neglected at the distribution voltage level (medium level).

The load flow studies are based on a nodal voltage analysis of a power system. The results of load flow analysis are used to understand the behavior of the system at different operating conditions. Hence, computation of a load flow is a basic requirement. And at present time there are many tools and software packages available. Well known commercial products such as Power System Simulator for Engineering (PSS), Digsilent, ETAP and Power World (Power World, 2016) are already available for power system studies, which can be customized according to requirements. These propriety software packages provide only end results but not the intermediate calculations. There are several algorithms for carrying out load flow analysis of power systems and many research papers are available as well. There are four important algorithms called Gauss Seidel (GS) Method, Newton-Raphson (NR) Method, Fast Decoupled (FDC) Method, and DC Load Flow Analysis. In this thesis, we deal with NR method. NR method is a very popular and faster solution for load flows analysis. This method requires an initial condition and works well for heavily loaded systems, when compared to other methods. Since the feeder line is heavily loaded NR method is preferred for the load flow analysis. After the execution of the load flow program using Matlab the power flow results are generated. However, for the purpose of the thesis only the voltage profile and power losses are tabulated here in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Voltage profile for KO5 feeder

Bus No	Voltage	Bus No	Voltage	Bus No	Voltage	Bus No	Voltage
1	1	29	0.8906	57	0.8361	85	0.8258
2	0.9976	30	0.8784	58	0.8358	86	0.8258
3	0.9973	31	0.8783	59	0.8354	87	0.8258
4	0.9973	32	0.8565	60	0.8354	88	0.8257
5	0.9967	33	0.855	61	0.8301	89	0.8256
6	0.9967	34	0.855	62	0.8299	90	0.8257
7	0.9955	35	0.8529	63	0.8297	91	0.8226
8	0.9949	36	0.8528	64	0.8297	92	0.8226
9	0.9949	37	0.8528	65	0.8296	93	0.8183
10	0.9944	38	0.8525	66	0.8297	94	0.8175
11	0.9955	39	0.8518	67	0.8296	95	0.8175
12	0.995	40	0.8518	68	0.8296	96	0.8159
13	0.9919	41	0.8512	69	0.8294	97	0.8159
14	0.9918	42	0.8512	70	0.8281	98	0.8146
15	0.9933	43	0.851	71	0.8267	99	0.8146
16	0.9846	44	0.851	72	0.826	100	0.8146
17	0.9846	45	0.8508	73	0.8247	101	0.8146
18	0.9694	46	0.8508	74	0.8245	102	0.8146
19	0.9605	47	0.8507	75	0.8251	103	0.8146
20	0.9108	48	0.8507	76	0.825	104	0.814
21	0.9108	49	0.8506	77	0.8246	105	0.814
22	0.9064	50	0.8511	78	0.8242	106	0.8135
23	0.9061	51	0.851	79	0.8243	107	0.8135
24	0.9061	52	0.8508	80	0.8242	108	0.8179
25	0.9058	53	0.8518	81	0.8241	109	0.8178
26	0.8995	54	0.839	82	0.8355	110	0.8178
27	0.8995	55	0.838	83	0.8353	111	0.8176
28	0.8906	56	0.8364	84	0.826	112	0.8173

The system has a minimum voltage of 0.8135p.u and a maximum of 1p.u. Most of the feeder nodes have a weak bus voltage profile. Thus, nodes 20 up to node 112 have out of standard limit voltages i.e. of $\pm 5\%$ voltage deviation. (See Table 4.1). As it has calculated using Newton Raphson method, the feeder has a total real and reactive power loss of 1498.7637kW and 1481.4610kVAr respectively. Here, two big problems have identified in this thesis .The weak voltage profile and high power loss. There are many techniques used to solve the problem in the system. As discussed in the past chapters integration of distribution generation is best solution to improve the voltage profile while minimizing the power loss. Distributed Generator is the one of latest technology approach that provides reliable and robust transmission and distribution of power over the Grid. These DG units reduce the system power loss without enhancing the transmission cost or the expansion of the distributed system. The main challenge in such system is the localization of the DG units [55].

4.4. DG model and their types

In this thesis, the loads have modeled as constant power model. Based upon different point of view such as; type of connection and operation mode DG unit can be modeled as PV bus or PQ bus [45]. A DG unit, which has already modeled as PQ bus can also, modeled into three other types such as DG unit with constant P and Q, DG unit with a certain specified value of P and power factor (PF) and as a varying Q generator DG unit can also be modeled. A DG unit having specified real power and bus voltage magnitude has modeled as PV bus DG unit [45].

DGs with smaller capacity and in the form of constant PQ model are sufficient for the loss minimization of a radial distribution system. For simplicity DG unit as negative load has assumed in this presented research paper.

Due to the availability of environmental effect of the DGs not all types of DGs were considered. Only two types of DGs were used (Photovoltaic and Wind), the first one was made to generate active power while the latter can generate both active and reactive power. Photovoltaic PV is operating at unity power factor (pf) while the wind is operating at 0.85 pf. This pf is selected for design purpose. Using the following proposed optimization methods, these high-power loss and weak voltage profile problems have optimized. Different scenarios

have been analyzed to improve this problem. Each scenario (see chapter 5) has been done based on different numbers and types of DGs.

4.5. Proposed Method

This section presents the technique used to solve the above problems. Both power flow and the optimization methods are used. The programme has implemented using GA optimization toolbox and Matlab 2013a software. This thesis has developed two stages with taking previous problems in our considerations. In the first stage, loss sensitivity analysis (LSF) is employed to select the most appropriate candidate buses for the DG unit's placement's. The second stage, a genetic algorithm is implemented to find the optimal sizing of DGs .NR algorithm is used for the power flow it is easy to implement, fast, flexible, robust convergence, and it has highly solution accuracy.

4.5.1. Loss sensitivity analysis (LSF) for optimal DG placement

In distribution systems power loss is not avoidable, but can be minimized to an optimum level due to DGs. Otherwise, researches have indicated that improperly DG allocation and power capacity identification can lead to an increase in system power loss [64], [65]. The operating condition of distribution systems drastically changes upon the connection of the DG compared to a system without DG. Planning the installation of DGs should therefore be considered such as the maximum number of DGs that can be connected into the system and at what capacities, where these DG units should be installed, what technology suits best, and what connection type should be used, among others. Previous studies have also shown that connecting DG at non-optimal locations increases the system's technical loss and therefore increases the cost of electricity, [37], [41]. Hence, it is crucial to find out the best location of DGs in order to reduce system power loss.

Loss Sensitivity Factor (LSF) method has been broadly widespread in the field of capacitor placement [66]. The application of this method in DG allocation is recent and has been reported in [67]. The main objective of this method is to identify the best locations for DG placement in distribution system based on power loss minimization.

The total system power loss has also formulated as exact loss formula, which includes real and reactive power losses respectively. The Exact Real power loss has given by equation (39)

$$P_{loss} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \left[a_{ij} (P_i P_j + Q_i Q_j) + b_{ij} (Q_i P_j - P_i Q_j) \right] \quad (39)$$

$$a_{ij} = \frac{R_{ij}}{V_i V_j} \cos (\delta_i - \delta_j) \quad (40)$$

$$b_{ij} = \frac{R_{ij}}{V_i V_j} \sin (\delta_i - \delta_j) \quad (41)$$

The Exact Reactive power loss is given by

$$Q_{loss} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \left[c_{ij} (P_i P_j + Q_i Q_j) + d_{ij} (Q_i P_j - P_i Q_j) \right] \quad (42)$$

$$c_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij}}{V_i V_j} \cos (\delta_i - \delta_j)$$

$$d_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij}}{V_i V_j} \sin (\delta_i - \delta_j) \quad (43)$$

Where,

n is the number of lines

a_{ij}, b_{ij}, c_{ij} and d_{ij} are function of loss coefficient between bus i and j.

P_i is real power flow at bus i in kW

Q_i is reactive power flow at bus i in kVAr

P_j is real power flow at bus j in kW

Q_j is reactive power flow at bus j in kVAr

V_i and V_j are bus voltage magnitude at bus i and j in PU

δ_i and δ_j are bus voltage angle at bus i and j

And the Total impedance between the bus i and bus j is given by

$$Z_{ij} = R_{ij} + jX_{ij} \quad (44)$$

Where

R_{ij} is Resistance of the line connecting bus i and j in Ohms

X_{ij} is Reactance of the line connecting bus i and j in Ohms

The real power loss in the system is given by exact loss formula stated in equation (39). The sensitivity factor of real power loss with respect to real power injection is obtained by differentiating exact loss formula with respect to real power injection at bus P_i which is given by [65], [68], [69]:

$$LSF = \frac{\delta P_{loss}}{\delta P_i} = 2 \sum_{j=1}^n (\alpha_{ij} P_j - \beta_{ij} Q_j) \quad (45)$$

The total power loss against injected power is a parabolic function and at minimum of losses, the rate of change of real power loss with respect to real power injection becomes zero.

Steps to determine the loss sensitivity factor (LSF)

1. Read the bus data and line data
2. Run the load flow using NR algorithm to determine the voltage magnitude with angles at each bus.
3. Determine the bus impedance matrix $[Z_{bus}]$
4. Determine the loss coefficients α_{ij} and β_{ij} using equation (40) and (41) respectively.
 - a. Determine the loss sensitivity factor using equation(45)
 - b. Locate the DGs at the most sensitive place

Following the above steps the first single optimal solution is determined. All DG locations were not selected in base load flow only. Here is the new method to determine the next best location for the second DG placement. The system has updated after the integration of the

first DG. Hence, continual update has taken successively to determine the place for the next DGs. after integrating the first DG. After that, the load data has updated with the first DG placed and then another DG has added. Similarly, the algorithm continues to allocate other DG units until it does not satisfy at least one of the constraints [45].

4.5.2. Genetic algorithm for sizing of optimal DG

Genetic algorithm has used as an optimization tool to solve the above-mentioned problem. Genetic algorithm under load flow analysis has used to find the size of DG and then calculate the power losses. [70], [71]. GAs are able to reach a good solution with high probability to be the best one by a finite steps of evolution steps performed on a finite set of possible solutions.

The solving of placement and sizing of DG unit's problem requires to define the Fitness Function that can be optimized in the presence of some constraints. The fitness function has selected for reducing power losses and increasing of voltage profile in the system or reducing cumulative voltage deviation. GA starts the process by automatically proposing different DG sizes within the proposed DG size limits and internally executes the load flow program that is properly linked with GA package till the minimum solution is obtained for the suggested location. This process has repeated for each of the proposed locations. Different scenarios have proposed to consider multiple of DG's at different suggested locations and to consider both DG PV and PQ models to determine the best location and size of the DG's. [72]. With the objective of power loss reduction and voltage profile improvement the fitness function or objective function (OF) is selected as follows [53], [54].

Algorithm for DG allocation in distribution system:

1. Generate random population of N_{POP} chromosomes.
2. Evaluate the objective function $F(x)$ and fitness $f(x)$ of each chromosome x in the population
3. Select the pairs of chromosome as parents from the population with giving a priority that the better fitness parents will get highest chance to be selected in the matting pool.
4. According to the matting pool parents are crossed over with a crossover probability and generate the offspring.

5. Now the crossed offspring are mutated with a mutation probability where the offspring locus is change slightly.
6. Consider the mutate offspring as a new population and use it for the next generation.
7. If the solution satisfied the end condition, then stop, and display the optimal solution.

4.5.3. Assumptions for Genetic Algorithm

As discussed in [37] Prior to the load flow analysis of the system, the number of populations and generations must be initially set to determine whether these populations and generations can have an effect in finding the optimal size and location. Tests have conducted to verify whether the statements are true or false. A successive population tests has selected for test purpose. Hundred numbers, fifty, and twenty chromosomes between the maxima and minima of the DG size has selected randomly for the first population. After the calculation, a probability has assigned to every chromosome that illustrates its fitness. The first test gives good result.

Further, increasing the population size to twenty and generations unchanged, the probability of finding the best result drastically increases because every simulation of the proposed algorithm shows only the result of the fittest. Further increasing the population size to hundred and generation still unchanged, the results of finding the fittest child suddenly decreases just like in having an initial population of five. On the other hand, when trying to decrease or increase the number of generations from the recommended generations of twenty generations, the result is the same as increasing or decreasing the number of populations. Meaning, finding the best solution or optimal result decreases when both population and generation are decreased. Finding the initial population size is very important due to it having an effect on the evaluation of the fitness function. Having a small initial population means, it improves initial performance while having a large initial population size improves long-term performance.

As described by [30], the best initial population size ranges from twenty to thirty. Further, population size is a parameter setting that will have an effect to the evaluation of the fitness function or objective function and it indicates the performance of GA. The entire algorithm is based on randomness. GA is an algorithm of random search; repeatability of results is a concern. To address this issue, ten independent runs/tests/iterations have made to verify the high probability of the results. Selection function is what chooses parents that will be needed in

the creation of the next generation. Roulette wheel selection was used because the chromosomes with the bigger fitness will likely be selected many times to produce the next set of generation. Meaning roulette wheel based selection will produce fitter results compare to other selection methods such as ordinal selection wherein the chromosomes are chosen randomly.

- Generations – 200
- Initial Population – 200
- Selection Function – Roulette Wheel

The genetic algorithm optimizes the loss given below

$$\text{Minimize } S_{loss} = \sum_{i=1}^n (P_{loss} + Q_{loss}) \quad (46)$$

Total active power loss in distribution system is given by

$$P_{loss} = \min \sum_{i=1}^n (I_i^2 \cdot R_i) \quad (47)$$

Total reactive power loss in distribution system is given by

$$Q_{loss} = \min \sum_{i=1}^n (I_i^2 \cdot X_i) \quad (48)$$

Where,

n is the number of lines at bus i ,

I_i is the line current at bus i in ohms,

R_i is the line resistance in ohms and X is line reactance at bus i in ohms respectively.

4.6. Objective Function

A precise evaluation for the Objective Function has been selected. The main goal of the proposed method is to determine the best locations and size for new Distributed Generation resources by minimizing different function, related to the thesis aims. It is clear that the different parts of the objective function do not have the same importance. So, each part has considered with a weight. Two main goals have taken into considerations to determine the Objective Formula that is used in point of start: Power Losses reduction and voltage profile improvement. The Fitness Function is determined as following.[73]

$$FF = W_P \cdot P_L + W_Q \cdot Q_L + W_V \cdot CVD \quad (49)$$

Where:

P_L : active power loss;

Q_L : reactive power loss;

W_P : weight for active power

W_Q : weight for reactive power

W_V : weight for voltage

CVD : cumulative voltage deviation;

FF : Fitness function (Objective function)

The active and reactive power losses have obtained from load flow program. The cumulative voltage deviation norm has described as “the normalized summation of the deviations of the gained value from the desired value at every node on the feeder”. The desired value being 1.0 p.u and the obtained value being the value collected from the three-phase distribution power flow solution. W_P , W_Q and W_V are objective function weights and these have evaluated as:

$$FF = W_P + W_Q + W_V = 1 \quad (50)$$

Minimization of voltage deviation Bus voltage is one of the important security and service quality indices. To improve the voltage profile the load bus voltage deviation should be minimized. This can be calculated as follows

$$CVD = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (1 - V_i) \right] \quad (51)$$

4.6.1. Choice of Weights values

The sharing of the different weights in a certain multi-objective function differs based on the engineer’s interest. In this research work, more emphasizes is given to real power loss reduction. However, this is not to mean that the other two elements are not significant. Thus taking this into consideration a study of the effect of the weights on the fitness has done to

determine the best weights combination to adopt in coming up with the multi-objective function. Throughout this study the values of the weights were supposed positive and restricted as follows:[38]

- W_p was restricted between 0.5 and 0.8 and
- W_Q and W_V were restricted between 0.1 and 0.4

Table 4.2: Weights for best fitness

W_p	W_Q	W_V	Best Fitness
0.5	0.1	0.4	4.936
0.5	0.2	0.3	3.7051
0.5	0.3	0.2	2.4733
0.5	0.4	0.1	1.2415
0.6	0.1	0.3	3.7070
0.6	0.2	0.2	2.4752
0.6	0.3	0.1	1.2471
0.7	0.1	0.2	2.4771
0.7	0.2	0.1	1.2453
0.8	0.1	0.1	1.2472

From the results presented in the above Table 4.2, the combination of weights chosen is the one that gave the minimum or best fitness. Since the power loss reduction and voltage profile improvement have more importance than voltage deviation problems, the weight factor for the loss, profile function and voltage deviations are chosen as 0.5, 0.4 and 0.1 respectively. Thus, fitness function has given by;

$$FF = 0.5P_L + 0.4Q_L + 0.1CVD \quad (52)$$

4.6.2. Constraints

In this thesis, the following constraints have applied to get optimal solution.

Active and reactive loss constraints

$$\begin{aligned} P_{LDG} &\leq P_{LBC} \\ Q_{LDG} &\leq Q_{LBC} \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

Where

P_{LBC} = active power loss before DG allocation

Q_{LBC} = Reactive power loss before DG allocation

- **Voltage constraints:**

$$V_{min} \leq V_i \leq V_{max} \quad (54)$$

Where

V_i = i bus voltage

V_{min} = minimum bus voltage

V_{max} = maximum bus voltage

- **Feeder line current limits should not be violated**

$$|I_{ij}| = |I_{ij}|_{scheduled} \quad (55)$$

Where, $|I_{ij}|_{scheduled}$ is the current carrying capacity of line section ij .

- **DG size constraints**

In this thesis, it was considered that the total power supplied by DG is not more than total demand [74]. This is done because supplying power to the external grid may increase the losses due to increased line flows. As in real networks, the reverse power flow can happen, and this constraint can be altered to allow a certain amount of power to be delivered to the external grid. Therefore, the size of the DG should be below the maximum load.

$$25\%L \leq DGs \leq 75\%L \quad (56)$$

Where

L = load capacity

DGs = size of DG

4.7. Over all algorithm

The procedure to allocate multiple DG is described in detail as follows.

Step 1: Select the number of DG units to be installed.

Step 2: Run load flow for the base case and find losses and voltage profiles

Step 3: Set the power factor of DG

Step 4: Find the optimal location of DG using LSF:

Step 5: Find the optimal size of DG and calculate losses using GA and NR.

Step 6: Update load data after placing the DG with the optimal size obtained in step 5 to allocate the next DG.

Step 7: Stop if either the following occurs:

- a) The voltage at a particular bus is over the upper limit;
- b) The total size of DG units is over the total load plus loss;
- c) The maximum number of DG units is unavailable;
- d) The new iteration loss is greater than the previous iteration loss.

The previous iteration loss has retained; otherwise, repeat steps 2 to 6.

Figure 4.4 Overall DG sizing and placement algorithm

4.8. Cost analysis

The economics attributes of energy loss, active and reactive power of DG considered based on the energy loss cost formula.

Energy Loss (EL): The cost of energy loss on annual basis is given by[37]

$$EL_{cost} = (Total\ real\ power\ loss). (E.T)Birr \quad (57)$$

Where

$$E=0.6949 \text{ Birr/kWh}$$

$$T = 8760 \text{ hours/year}$$

Cost attributes of DG is selected as per the data

$$C(P_{DG}) = aP_{DG}^2 + bP_{DG} + cP_{DG} \quad Birr / KWHr \quad (58)$$

Where a = 0.25; b = 20; c = 0.

Cost of reactive power as[37], [75] with K=0.05 to 0.1

$$C(Q_{DG}) = \left[\left[Cost(Sg_{max}) - Cost\left(\sqrt{Sg_{max}^2 - Q_g^2}\right) \right] \right] \times K \text{ Birr} / Hr \quad (59)$$

$$Sg_{max} = \frac{Pg_{max}}{\cos\phi}$$

$$P_{max} = 1.1Pg$$

$$K = 0.05 \text{ upto } 1$$

In this thesis, the k factor has assumed as 0.1.

CHAPTER 5

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Introduction

In this chapter, the results obtained using load flow, GA and LSF methods have presented. At last the savings from the optimization are also presented. The results have presented in graph and table form. The algorithm outlined in the previous chapter have implemented and programed in Matlab 2013a. The main codes programmed according to the implementation steps of the proposed algorithm have given in Appendix-B. The results have subdivided into different scenarios depending on the test bus system under consideration and the type of DG being optimally place and sized. Different comparisons have done to show in reducing network losses and improving voltage profile in relation to other DG types and sizes.

5.2. Load Flow and Optimization Results

5.2.1. Scenario 0: Load Flow at Base Case

In case 0, the system has analyzed without adding distributed generation. Power losses, voltage profile and voltage deviation are the results. Therefore, in this case the whole active and reactive power generation comes from the substation. The voltage profiles of all the system buses are not within required range. Minimum voltage magnitude has recorded at bus 106 and 107 and the value of voltage magnitude is 0.8135p.u. These two buses has an approximated same voltage level .This happened because of the distance between the two buses is very small. So it can be neglected and we can take one of the two buses instead of both. All voltages at all nodes are less than one per unit. Moreover, all buses beyond bus 22 are out of the standard voltage level. See all the voltage profile results in Table 4.1.

The active and reactive power losses are 1498.7637 and 1481.461 kVAr respectively. It is not economical to lose this much power. So a method is needed to fix it. As discussed in last chapters DGs are the best solutions. Thus, the next scenarios have a solution for it.

Figure 5.1 Voltage magnitudes before DG placement

Loss sensitivity approach

Sensitivity factors are evaluated at each bus, firstly by using the values obtained at base case load flows. The buses have ranked in descending order of the values of sensitivity factors to form a priority list. The bus with highest loss sensitivity used as optimal location. Table 5.1 shows the loss sensitivity results for the five most loss sensitive buses. The loss sensitivity is in a descendent order. The bus with high LSF is the best location for DG placement[76],[77]. As shown from Table 5.1 bus number 107 is the most loss sensitive bus. Thus from the loss sensitivity result; the researcher has decided to place the first single DG at that bus.

Table 5.1: Five most loss sensitive buses before the integration DGs

Loss sensitivity ($\times 10^4$)	Bus number
5.878	107
5.8779	106
5.8579	105
5.8577	104
5.837	103

Figure 5.2 Loss Sensitivity of all nodes before the integration of DGs

The results shown above in Figure 5.2 are the loss sensitivities at each node of the network. As it is seen from that figure most of the nodes around the end of the feeder have high loss sensitivities.

Result Summary:

Fitness function	1.5139
CVD	15
Loss sensitive bus	107
Minimum voltage	0.8135p.u
Real power loss	1498.7 kW
Reactive power loss	1481.5 kVAr
DG capacity	No DG

5.2.2. Scenario 1: Single PV type DG is Considered

In scenario 1, a single PV type distributed generation is connected to the network. After the genetic algorithm based optimization is executed, the value of the active power of the DG is determined as 6.57 MW.

Figure 5.3 Voltage magnitude after the integration of single DG

Figure 5.4 Voltage magnitude Comparison of scenario 0 up to scenario 1

Allocating this DG unit at bus 107 enhances the system optimization. The power flow result of the updated system has given in Figure 5.3 and Figure 5.4 the active and reactive powers have optimized to 544.616kW and 537.36Mvar respectively. The real power and reactive power losses have minimized by 63.66% and 63.72% respectively. Voltage profile improvement in the network have displayed above in Figure 5.4 After integration of DG, it has observed that all the buses have improved slightly. The load flow without DG bus 107 has recorded the worst voltage value, in comparison with the other buses. After the integration of single DG, it has improved to 0.9256pu. Certain of the buses were well within the usual standard level, but others were not good indeed. Although, the system is reasonably improved, but still needs an improvement. As shown below in Figure 5.4 most buses are sensitive to power loss. After update, bus 81 is the most sensitive bus. Therefore, the second DGs have integrated at that bus.

Table 5.2: Five most loss sensitive buses at scenario 1

LSF ($\times 10^4$)	Bus number
1.2551	81
1.2521	80
1.252	78
1.2493	79
1.2439	74

Figure 5.5 Loss sensitivities of all nodes at scenario 1

Result summary:

Fitness function	0.722
CVD	7.17
Loss sensitive bus	81
Minimum voltage	0.9085p.u
Real power loss	544.6 kW
Reactive power loss	537.4 kVAr
DG capacity	DG1: 6.57MW (at bus 107)

5.2.3. Scenario 2: Two PV type DGs are considered

As shown in Figure 5.5, the trend of losses sensitivities is captured which is good enough to identify the best location of the next DG that would lead to the least total power losses.

Figure 5.6 Voltage profile after the integration of two PV type DGs

Figure 5.7 Voltage magnitudes Comparisons of scenario 0 up to scenario 2

The optimal solution that minimizes the objective function has found at buses 107 and 81 with sizes of the PVs at 4.61 MW and 1.96 MW respectively. Here, total real power losses have reduced to 487.67 kW from 1498.76 kW. This indicates a reduction of about 67.5 % from the pre-installation case. In addition, total reactive power losses have reduced to 1481.5 kVAr from 480.3 kVAr. This indicates a reduction of about 67.58 % from the pre-installation case. After integration of the second DG, it has observed that all the buses have improved considerably. Although the system was improved somewhat, but it needs additional improvement. The voltages were not within the standard limit of $\pm 5\%$ voltage deviation. The voltage profile results have tabulated above in Figure 5.6.

Table 5.3: Five most loss sensitive nodes

LSF (x104)	Bus number
9.9734	49
9.9572	48
9.9558	47
9.9183	46
9.9082	45

Figure 5.8 Loss sensitivities of all nodes

Result summary

Fitness function	0.7137
CVD	7.09
Loss sensitive bus	49
Minimum voltage	0.9172p.u
Real power loss	487.69 kW
Reactive power loss	480.35kVAr
DG capacity	DG1: 4.61MW(at bus 107) DG2: 1.96MW(at bus 81)

5.2.4. Scenario 3: Three PV type DGs are considered

The optimal DGs location that minimizes the objective function was found at buses 107, 81 and 49, with a capacity of 5.11 MW, 732.2 kW and 728.92 kW respectively. Here, total real power losses have reduced to 493.8 kW from 1499 kW and reactive power losses also reduced to 487.3 kVAr from 1481.5kVAr. This indicates a reduction of about 67.06 % and 67.12% respectively, from the pre-installation case. The voltage level has improved from 0.8135p.u lowest voltage at bus 107 to 0.9199p.u. Integration three DGs have an additional improvement from the past scenarios. This scenario is better than the first two scenarios. Despite the good improvements of power loss, the voltage profiles were not improved to the standard limit of $\pm 5\%$ voltage deviation. Figure 5.9 (below) shows voltage profile at each bus. Figure 5.10 shows the Voltage Profile Comparison before and after the integration of Three PV type DGs.

Figure 5.9 Voltage magnitudes of all nodes at scenario 3

Figure 5.10 Voltage magnitudes Comparisons of scenario 0 up to scenario 3

Result summary:

Fitness function	0.72
CVD	7.158
Loss sensitive bus	74
Minimum voltage	0.9116p.u
Real power loss	493.8 kW
Reactive power loss	487.28 kVAr
DG capacity	DG 1: 5.11MW(at bus 107) DG 2: 732.2kW (at bus 81) DG 3: 728.92kW(at bus 49)

Table 5.4: Over all comparison between different number of PV DGs

DG type	DG No.	Bus No.	DG size (MW)	Power loss		Voltage profile		Percentage of Power loss reduction	
				Real (kW)	Reactive (kVAr)	Minimum (p.u)	Maximum (p.u)	Real	Reactive
-	-	-	-	1498.8	1481.5	0.8135	1.00	-	-
PV	1	107	6.57	544.62	537.36	0.9085	1.00	63.66	63.72
	2	107	4.61	487.7	480.4	0.9172	1.00	67.5	67.58
		81	1.96						
	3	107	5.11	493.8	487.3	0.9116	1.00	67.06	67.12
		81	0.732						
		49	0.729						

5.2.5. Scenario 4: Single PQ type DG is Considered

Scenario 4 discusses the result about the integration of single PQ type DG. A single PQ type distributed generation has connected to the network at bus 107. This bus has chosen according to the results found from the load flow of the network without DG. (See Figure 5.2) .Most of the DGs in market have around 0.85 power factor. Thus, the power factor of the DG has assumed as 0.85. The active and reactive power capacity of the DG is determined as 6.57 MW and 4.07kVAr respectively.

Figure 5.11 Voltage magnitude after the integration of single PQ type DG

Figure 5.12 Voltage magnitude Comparison of scenario 0 and scenario 4

Integrating the determined DG unit at bus 107 enhances the optimization system. As a result, the power flow voltage profile of the updated system has given in Figure 5.12. The active and reactive power losses have optimized to 145.1kW and 142 kVAr respectively. The real power and reactive power losses has minimized by 90.33%and 90.42% respectively. Voltage profile improvement in the network has displayed above in Figure 5.12. After integration of DG, it was observed that all the buses are improved to the standard limit of $\pm 5\%$ voltage deviation. The load flow without DG bus 107 was recorded the worst voltage value, in comparison with the other buses. After the integration of single DG, it has improved to 0.9868pu. The systems voltage profile power loss is reasonably improved.

Table 5.5: Five most loss sensitive buses

LSF ($\times 10^3$)	Bus number
9.8959	81
9.8698	80
9.8694	78
9.8459	79
9.7988	74

Figure 5.13 Loss sensitivities of all nodes

Result summary:

Fitness function	0.2876
CVD	2.86
Loss sensitive bus	81
Minimum voltage	0.9551p.u
Real power loss	145.12 kW
Reactive power loss	141.9 kVAr
DG capacity	DG1: P:6.57MW (at bus 107) Q:4.07MVAR

5.2.6. Scenario 5: Two PQ type DGs are considered

As shown in Figure 5.13, the trend of losses sensitivities is captured which is good enough to identify the best location of the next DG that would lead to the least total power losses.

Figure 5.14 Voltage profile after the integration of two PQ type DGs

Figure 5.15 Voltage magnitudes Comparison of scenario 0, scenario 4 and scenario 5

The optimal solution that minimizes the objective function has found at buses 107 and 81. The active and reactive power capacity of the first DG has calculated as 4.7 MW and 2.9 MVAR respectively. The active and reactive power capacity of the first DG is calculated as 1.87 MW and 1.16 MVAR respectively. Both DGs have a power factor of 0.85. Here, total real power losses have reduced to 84.57 kW from 1498.76 kW. This indicates a reduction of about 94.4 % from the pre-installation case. In addition, total reactive power losses have reduced to 81.02 kVAr from 1481.5 kVAr. This indicates a reduction of about 94.6 % from the pre-installation case. After integration of the second DG, it was observed that all the buses voltage was improved to the standard limit of $\pm 5\%$ voltage deviation. The voltage profile results have tabulated above in figure 5.15. The system has totally improved to its standard value. Therefore, it may not need any further improvement. Nevertheless, for comparison purpose it is better to see the impact of three PQ type DGs on the feeder.

Table 5.6: Five most loss sensitive nodes

LSF ($\times 10^3$)	Bus number
7.8377	49
7.8232	48
7.822	47
7.7887	46
7.7797	45

Figure 5.16 Loss sensitivities of all nodes

Result summary

Fitness function	0.279
CVD	2.782

Loss sensitive bus	49
Minimum voltage	0.965p.u
Real power loss	84.56 kW
Reactive power loss	81.02 MVAR
DG capacity	DG1:
Pf=0.85	P: 4.7 MW(at bus 107)
	Q: 2.91 kVAr
	DG2:
	P: 1.87 MW(at bus 81)
	Q: 1.16 MVAR

5.2.7. Scenario 6: Three PQ type DGs are considered

The optimal DGs location that minimizes the objective function was found at buses 107, 81 and 49. The size of the DGs is determined by using GA algorithm. The capacity of the first DG is determined as 5.11 MW 3.17 MVAR, 730.5 kW and 452.7kVAr is the size of the second DG. The size of the third DG has also calculated to be 730kW and 452.3kVAr respectively. Here, total real power losses have reduced to 91.7 kW from 1499 kW and reactive power losses also reduced to 89.5 kVAr from 1481.5kVAr. This indicates a reduction of about 93.9 % and 94% respectively, from the pre-installation case. The voltage profiles are also improved. There is an increment in power loss from the past scenario 5. Nonetheless; there is good improvement from the other past scenarios.

In spite of the good improvements of power loss and voltage profiles in this scenario, it is better to install two PQ type DGs. The updated voltage profiles at each bus are given in Figure 5.17. Figure 5.18 shows the Voltage Profile Comparison before and after the integration of three PV type DGs.

Figure 5.17 Voltage profiles of all nodes at scenario 6

Figure 5.18 Voltage magnitudes Comparison of scenario 0, scenario 4, scenario 5 and scenario 6

Table 5.7: Over all comparison between different number of PQ DGs

DG type	DG No.	Bus No.	DG size (MW)	Power loss		Voltage profile		Percentage of Power loss reduction		
				Real (kW)	Reactive (kVAr)	Minimum (p.u)	Maximum (p.u)	Real	Reactive	
-	-	-	-	1498.8	1481.5	0.8135	1.00	-	-	
PQ	1	107	6.57+j4.1	145.1	142	0.955	1.00	90.33	90.42	
		81	1.87+j1.16	84.57	81.02	0.965	1.00	94.4	94.6	
	107	4.7+j2.91								
	3	81	107	5.11+j3.17	91.7	89.5	0.959	1.00	93.9	94
			107	0.73+j0.453						
		49	0.730+j452.3							

Result summary:

Fitness function	0.29
CVD	2.8959
Loss sensitive bus	74
Minimum voltage	0.959p.u
Real power loss	91.7 kW
Reactive power loss	89.5 kVAr
DG capacity	DG 1: 5.11MW and 3.17MVAR (at bus 107)
Pf =0.85	DG 2: 730kW and 453kVAr (at bus 81)
	DG 3: 730kW and 523kVAr (at bus 49)

5.2.8. Scenario 7: One PQ type and One PV type DGs are considered**Result summary:**

Fitness function	0.348
CVD	0.3468
Loss sensitive bus	49
Minimum voltage	0.953p.u
Real power loss	135.6 kW
Reactive power loss	131.79 kVAr
DG capacity	DG 1: 5.47MW and 3.39MVAR (at bus 107)
	Pf=0.85
	DG 2: 1.1MW (at bus 81)

5.2.9. Scenario 8: One PQ type and Two PV type DGs are considered

Result summary:

Fitness function	0.4863
CVD	4.8447
Loss sensitive bus	74
Minimum voltage	0.9418p.u
Real power loss	206.92 kW
Reactive power loss	202.65 kVAr
DG capacity	DG 1: 3.4 MW and 2.11MVAR (at bus 107) DG 2: 2.17MW (at bus 81) DG 3: 998.5kW (at bus 49)

5.2.10. Scenario 9: Two PQ type and 1PV type DGs are considered

Result summary:

Fitness function	0.2789
CVD	2.7862
Loss sensitive bus	74
Minimum voltage	0.965p.u
Real power loss	83.98 kW
Reactive power loss	80.55 kVAr
DG capacity	DG 1: 4.38MW and 2.71 MVAR (at bus 107) DG 2: 2.19MW and 1.36MVAR (at bus 81) DG 3: 34.6W (at bus 49)

The result summary has given under scenario-7 up to scenario-9 are discussing about the impact of the combination of the two DG types on the feeder. The optimization comparison is tabulated in Table 5.8. Generally, Figure 5.19 (a) presents the comparison of the three scenarios that considers both DG types. From these cases, the combination of two PQ type and one PV type DGs has found as the best solution for the system improvement. In the same way, the best of the combinations has compared with the best of the PV and PQ type DGs individually. Finally, scenario-9 has found as the best solution for the system improvement. (See Figure 5.19).

The bar graph shown in Figure 5.20 presents the objective function for the system optimization. Thus, the objective function has optimized by using 2PQ and 1PV type DGs. Finally, the active and reactive power losses of the system have minimized by 94.4% and 94.6%, and the CVD is limited to 2.78.

Table 5.8: Result Comparison for both types of DG

DG type	DG No.	Bus No.	DG size (MW)	Power loss		Voltage profile		Percentage of Power loss reduction	
				P _{loss} (kW)	Q _{loss} (kVAr)	Minimum (p.u)	Maximum (p.u)	Real (%)	Reactive (%)
-	-	-	-	14989	1482	0.8135	1.00	-	-
PQ And PV	1PQ	107	5.47+j3.3	135.6	131.8	0.953	1.00	90.95	91.10
	1PV	81							
PV	1PQ	107	3.4+j2.1	207	202.6	0.942	1.00	86.2	86.32
		2PV							
	2PV	49	0.99						
2PQ 1PV	2PQ	107	4.38+j2.71	83.98	80.55	0.965	1.00	94.4	94.6
		81							
	1PV	49	0.000035						

Figure 5.19 Voltage magnitude comparisons of PV and PQ type DGs

Figure 5.20 Overall optimization of the objective function

As a result, the advantage of the optimal placement and sizing of DGs with the proposed method has illustrated clearly in Figure 5.1, Figure 5.12, Figure 5.18, and Figure 5.20. As mentioned in these figures, the minimum voltage before DG allocation was about 0.8135p.u approximately; whereas the maximum voltage was 1.0 p.u. in addition to that the active and reactive power loss was about 1499kW and 1481 kVAr respectively. After DG placement, all the scenarios minimized the power loss and they improved the voltage in the network; however, the voltage improvement is varying. It has already shown in Figure 5.19(a) and Figure 5.19(b) that voltage variation (the difference between maximum and minimum voltages appearing in the network) is the lowest when we consider one PQ DG,two PQ DGs,three PQ DGs ,one PQ DG and one PV DG ,and two PQ DGs and one PV DG. Although, all these scenarios can improve the power system but considering the installation cost and area needed scenario four has selected as the best solution. Finally ,bus number 107 has selected as the best node to place the required DG with their optimum size. The size of the DG has calculated to be 6.57 MW and 4.07 MVar . The ratings of the PQ type and PV types DGs is selected according to the genetic algorithm best fitness function.

Savings: So, integrating two PQ type and one PV type distribution generation in to the specified buses of KO5 feeder can save about 1415kW power. From this power, the company can save about 7,771,872Birr/year.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1. Conclusion

A novel approach incorporating the use of LSF method and GA optimization methods have presented in this thesis. This method has applied to determine the optimal number, locations, and sizes of DGs to place in feeder KO5 in Mekelle distribution systems. The LSF method used to determine the best location for the DG. Then by updating the load flow of the old feeder line network, optimization has done by genetic algorithm optimization technique. Based on Newton Raphson power flow method and using genetic algorithm, the best and fastest results have obtained for the sizing of the DG. The case study in this thesis has applied in Mekelle power distribution lines specifically in feeder line KO5. The feeder line has modelled as a single network that has 112 nodes and 64 loads. It has a total capacity of 10.5 MW.

At different parts of the feeder line, there are weak voltage profiles. Actually, the voltage profiles of most of the nodes in feeder are not in the acceptable voltage level (i.e. 0.95-1.05 pu interval). Moreover, the active and reactive power losses of the feeder are 1498.7637kW and 1481.461 kVAr respectively. A novel method-loss sensitivity based Newton Raphson-Genetic algorithm approach has implemented to optimize the location and size of the DG. This method places one DG at a time on a high loss sensitive bus and then it finds the corresponding power losses. After that, it stores the size of the DG corresponding to the least losses. For the next DGs, same practice continues until the specified stopping criterion has reached. In this thesis it has modeled a power system based on a standard system and has made a load flow analysis for different scenarios. It has been studied the impact that distributed generation has on the system. The scenarios have considered based on the type of DGs. PQ and PV type DGs have considered. Thus, in this thesis single PQ type DG has selected as the best solution to optimize the system. The total active power loss recorded in feeder has minimized to 145.1kW and the total reactive power loss has minimized to 142kVAr. In the same way all the weak voltage profiles have also optimized to the standard $\pm 5\%$ voltage deviation level. This thesis presents all about how to place and size DGs on feeder lines. And feeder line KO5 is taken as case

study. Power loss reduction and voltage profile improvements are the main constraints. The protection and impacts of the DGs is not considered here.

Since the system is interconnected power system, the feasibility of the design is economical. Integrating of two PQ type and one PV type distribution generation in to the specified buses of KO5 feeder can save about 1415kW power. From this power, the company can save about 7,771,872Birr/year.

6.2. Recommendation

- This thesis work only conducted on the KO5 feeder line, future works can use the same analysis to improve the power loss, and voltage profiles of the other feeder lines of the substation.
- Distributed generation may cause noticeable voltage flicker and introduce harmonics into the system. Further research could focus on the impacts of DG on the short circuit levels of the system and the harmonic distortion of the systems.
- The effect of increasing the grid fault current by adding generation often leads to improved power quality; however, it may also have a negative impact on other aspects of system performance (e.g., protection coordination). So Further research could also focus on the protection system of the systems.

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APPENDIX A

Lachi Substation network and Line data for feeder ko5

Line data for feeder ko5

FROM	TO	R(Ohm)	X(Ohm)
1	2	0.029433	0.030932
2	3	0.069587	0.041731
3	4	0.057586	0.018221
3	5	0.160991	0.096546
5	6	0.051949	0.031154
5	7	0.404487	0.242571
7	8	1.402284	0.84095
8	9	0.134212	0.080487
8	10	2.744404	1.64582
7	11	0.016198	0.009714
11	12	0.222723	0.133567
12	13	2.1036	1.261529
13	14	0.112634	0.067547
12	15	2.984366	1.789725
2	16	0.165418	0.173847
16	17	0.045586	0.027338
16	18	0.193244	0.203091
18	19	0.166875	0.052802
19	20	0.637361	0.669838
20	21	0.041099	0.013004
20	22	0.056394	0.059267
22	23	0.192756	0.115596
23	24	0.0479	0.028726
23	25	0.184542	0.11067
22	26	0.091779	0.096455
26	27	0.017529	0.010512
26	28	0.118464	0.1245

28	29	0.009448	0.00299
28	30	0.164122	0.172485
30	31	0.126518	0.075873
30	32	0.294216	0.309208
32	33	0.171236	0.10269
33	34	0.036793	0.022065
33	35	0.279011	0.167323
35	36	0.102568	0.06151
35	37	0.090825	0.054467
35	38	0.061437	0.036844
38	39	0.139361	0.083575
39	40	0.087527	0.05249
39	41	0.152898	0.091693
41	42	0.009025	0.005412
42	43	0.099271	0.059533
43	44	0.128965	0.040807
43	45	0.112345	0.067373
45	46	0.040264	0.024146
45	47	0.199438	0.119603
47	48	0.011223	0.00673
47	49	0.150063	0.089993
42	50	0.008793	0.005273
50	51	0.101006	0.060573
50	52	0.259747	0.15577
32	53	0.074349	0.078137
53	54	0.203857	0.214244
54	55	0.041031	0.043121
55	56	0.071942	0.075608
56	57	0.198426	0.118996

57	58	0.242623	0.145501
56	59	0.048033	0.050481
59	60	0.003394	0.003566
59	61	0.255747	0.268778
61	62	0.109741	0.065812
62	63	0.170658	0.102343
61	64	0.161402	0.096793
64	65	0.053974	0.032368
64	66	0.095221	0.057104
61	67	0.038563	0.040527
67	68	0.037255	0.022342
67	69	0.01938	0.011622
69	70	0.095493	0.100359
70	71	0.114608	0.120448
71	72	0.079902	0.083973
72	73	0.298628	0.313845
73	74	0.106741	0.11218
72	75	0.15354	0.161364
75	76	0.32155	0.337934
75	77	0.091933	0.096617
77	78	0.218356	0.229483
77	79	0.075891	0.079758
79	80	0.048681	0.051162
79	81	0.12448	0.130823
54	82	0.09255	0.097266
82	83	0.079023	0.04739
82	84	0.256734	0.269816
84	85	0.301155	0.095291
84	86	0.087816	0.052663

86	87	0.055536	0.033305
86	88	0.083379	0.026383
88	89	0.062829	0.01988
88	90	0.302218	0.095627
84	91	0.123105	0.073826
91	92	0.021231	0.012732
91	93	0.132161	0.138896
93	94	0.03702	0.038906
94	95	0.002661	0.001596
94	96	0.074349	0.078137
96	97	0.019553	0.011726
96	98	0.0588	0.061796
98	99	0.010057	0.01057
99	100	0.006711	0.004024
99	101	0.016777	0.010061
101	102	0.004397	0.002637
101	103	0.045817	0.027477
98	104	0.033071	0.034756
104	105	0.019127	0.020102
104	106	0.029925	0.031449
106	107	0.000021	0.002175
93	108	0.038871	0.040852
108	109	0.023719	0.014224
108	110	0.015919	0.01673
110	111	0.088632	0.093148
110	112	0.251746	0.150972

Appendix-A2: Bus data for feeder ko5

BUS NO.	PL(kW)	QL (kVAr)	BUS NO.	PL (kW)	QL (kVAr)	BUS NO.	PL (kW)	QL (kVAr)	BUS NO.	PL (kW)	QL (kVAr)
1	0	0	29	45.6	34.2	57	86.4	64.8	85	87.2	65.4
2	0	0	30	0	0	58	135.2	101.4	86	0	0
3	0	0	31	26.4	19.8	59	0	0	87	45.6	34.2
4	26.4	19.8	32	0	0	60	34.4	25.8	88	0	0
5	0	0	33	0	0	61	0	0	89	176	132
6	116.8	87.6	34	105.6	79.2	62	202.4	151.8	90	15.2	11.4
7	0	0	35	0	0	63	132	99	91	0	0
8	0	0	36	100.8	75.6	64	0	0	92	97.6	73.2
9	30.4	22.8	37	93.6	70.2	65	232	174	93	0	0
10	32	24	38	191.2	143.4	66	86.4	64.8	94	0	0
11	69.6	52.2	39	0	0	67	0	0	95	68.8	51.6
12	0	0	40	89.6	67.2	68	16.8	12.6	96	0	0
13	123.2	92.4	41	62.4	46.8	69	64	48	97	28	21
14	104.8	78.6	42	0	0	70	192.8	144.6	98	0	0
15	88.8	66.6	43	0	0	71	200	150	99	0	0
16	0	0	44	15.2	11.4	72	0	0	100	248.8	186.6
17	17.6	13.2	45	0	0	73	178.4	133.8	101	0	0
18	0	0	46	100.8	75.6	74	244	183	102	14.4	10.8

19	35.2	26.4	47	0	0	75	0	0	103	36	27
20	0	0	48	48.8	36.6	76	13.6	10.2	104	0	0
21	40	30	49	47.2	35.4	77	0	0	105	32.8	24.6
22	0	0	50	0	0	78	183.2	137.4	106	958.4	718.8
23	0	0	51	128	96	79	0	0	107	884.8	663.6
24	41.6	31.2	52	144.8	108.6	80	215.2	161.4	108	0	0
25	199.2	149	53	143.2	107.4	81	176	132	109	616	462
26	0	0	54	0	0	82	0	0	110	0	0
27	44.8	33.6	55	86.4	64.8	83	181.6	136.2	111	236	177
28	0	0	56	0	0	84	0	0	112	240	180

Appendix–A3: Ethiopian electric billing system

Types of premises	Category	Average monthly consumption range	Rate/Ethiopian Birr
Residential	1 st block	0-50	0.273
	2 st block	51-100	0.3564
	3 st block	101-200	0.4993
	4 st block	201-300	0.5500
	5 st block	301-400	0.5666
	6 st block	401-500	0.5880
	7 st block	>500	0.6943
Commercial (General)	1 st block	0-50	0.6088
	2 st block	>50	0.6943

Appendix-A4: Authorized Letter from EEP

Scanned by CamScanner

 የኢትዮጵያ ኤሌክትሪክ ኃይል ETHIOPIAN ELECTRIC POWER	Document No: OF/EEP/11-0036	
	ውስጣዊ ማስታወሻ	Issue No. 02 Page No. Page 1 of 10

ቀን : 19/08/2009 ዓ.ም

ቁጥር: 01/08/09

ለ : ትራንስሚሽን ሰብስቶችን አጥፊዎች

ከ : ሪጅናል አጥፊዎችን ኮሌጂዎችን ሲንተር

ክፍላይ ዘንብ
የሰሜን ሪጅን ትራንስሚሽን አጥፊዎች
ማስተባበር ሰራተኛ
Kiflay Zenebe
Regional Operation Co-ordinator

ጉዳዩ:- የመቀሌ ሰብስቶችን 15ኪ.ቪ ወጪ መስመሮች መመዘኛውን ማሳወቅ ይመለከታል::

በሰሜን ሪጅን ትራንስሚሽን ሰብስቶችን አጥፊዎች ስር የሚገኘው የመቀሌ ሰብስቶችን የ15ኪ.ቪ አራት ወጪ መስመሮች መጫን ከሚገባቸው ጭነት በላይ እየጫኑ ስለሆኑ የማስተካከያ ስራ እንዲሰራ አሳውቃለሁ::

No.	Substation	15KV Line	CT Ratio	Peak Load		Line Capacity (MW)	Cable Size (mm ²)
				Power (MW)	Current (A)		
1	Mekelle	KO10	200/400	12.5	500	8.8	240
2	Mekelle	KO3	200/400	11.2	447	8.8	240
3	Mekelle	KO4	200/400	11.1	445	8.8	240
4	Mekelle	KO5	200/400	10.5	420	8.8	240

ለሰሜን ሪጅን ትራንስሚሽን ሳብስተሽን አፕራሽን ቢሮ
መቀሌ

ጉዳይ :- ሳብስተሽን የደረሰው ከፍተኛ ጫነት ማሳወቅ ይሆናል

No	SUBSTATION	15 KV FEEDER	CT R	PEAK LOAD		TR CAPACITY		CABLE mm2
				POWER MW	CURRENT . A	MVA	MW	
1	MEKELLE	Ko .1	800/1600	31.8	1225	37.5	30	3 300
		Ko.7	800/1600	31.8	1225	37.5	30	3800

NB መቀሌ ሳብስተሽን ከፍተኛ የመጫን አቅም 30 ሜ.ዋ ሁኖ እያለ ከአቅሙ በላይ ተጫኖ አስከ 31.8 ሜ.ዋ አየደረሰ ስለሆነ ማስተካከያ እንዲደረግለት በማል በአካብሮት እጠይቃለሁ ::

ከሰላምታ ጋር

ክፍላይ ዘነበ
የሰሜን ሪጅን ትራንስሚሽን አፕራሽን
ማከተባበር ሰራ ሃላፊ
Kiflay Zenebe
Regional Operation Co-ordinator

09/06/09

Appendix–A5: Updated KO5 feeder network

APPENDIX-B

Algorithms for Power flow, loss sensitivities and Zbus formation are presented under this appendix. Finally Genetic algorithm for sizing and allocation of different types of DGs is

Appendix-B1: Sub Program for Load Flow

```
function ff=mekelle112bus(x)

linedata=xlsread('Linedata12345.xlsx');

send = linedata(:,1);

receive = linedata(:,2);

R = linedata(:,3);

X = linedata(:,4);

LineCharge = j*linedata(:,5);

a = linedata(:, 6);

ZZZZ=R+i*X;

xlswrite('impedance',ZZZZ);

NumberBranch=length(linedata(:,1));

NumberBus = max(max(send), max(receive));

Z = R + j*X;

MVAb=100;

KVb=15;

Zbase=(KVb.^2)/MVAb;

Zpu=Z./Zbase;
```

```

y= ones(NumberBranch,1)./Zpu;    %branch admittance

for n = 1:NumberBranch

Y=zeros(NumberBus,NumberBus);    % initialize Ybus to zero

% formation of the off diagonal elements

for k=1:NumberBranch;

    Y(send(k),receive(k))=Y(send(k),receive(k))-y(k)/a(k);

    Y(receive(k),send(k))=Y(send(k),receive(k));

end

end

% formation of the diagonal elements

for n=1:NumberBus

    for k=1:NumberBranch

        if send(k)==n

            Y(n,n) = Y(n,n)+y(k)/(a(k)^2) + LineCharge(k);

        elseif receive(k)==n

            Y(n,n) = Y(n,n)+y(k) +LineCharge(k);

        else

            end

        end

    end

end

BusData=xlsread('Busdata12.xlsx');

```

```

Bus = BusData(:,1);      % Bus Number..

BusType = BusData(:,2);  % Type of Bus 1-Slack, 2-PV, 3-PQ..

Vspe = BusData(:,3);     % Specified Voltage..

VolAngl = BusData(:,4);  % Voltage Angle..

Pg = BusData(:,5)/(1000*MVA); % PGi..

Qg = BusData(:,6)/(1000*MVA); % QGi..

Pl = BusData(:,7)/(1000*MVA); % PLi..

Ql = BusData(:,8)/(1000*MVA); % QLi..

Qmin = BusData(:,9)/(1000*MVA); % Minimum Reactive Power Limit..

Qmax = BusData(:,10)/(1000*MVA); % Maximum Reactive Power Limit..

P = Pg - Pl;            % Pi = PGi - PLi..

Q = Qg - Ql;           % Qi = QGi - QLi..

Psp = P;                % P Specified..

Qsp = Q;                % Q Specified..

G = real(Y);            % Conductance matrix..

B = imag(Y);            % Susceptance matrix..

PVbus = find(BusType == 2 | BusType == 1); % PV Buses..

PQbus = find(BusType == 3); % PQ Buses..

npv = length(PVbus);    % No. of PV buses..

NumPQ = length(PQbus);  % No. of PQ buses..

```

```

Tol = 1;

Iter = 1;

while (Tol > 1e-10) % Iteration starting..

    P = zeros(NumberBus,1);

    Q = zeros(NumberBus,1);

    % Calculate P and Q

    for ii = 1:NumberBus

        for k = 1:NumberBus

            P(ii) = P(ii) + Vspe(ii)* Vspe(k)*(G(ii,k)*(cos(VolAnгл(ii)-VolAnгл(k))) +
B(ii,k)*(sin(VolAnгл(ii)-VolAnгл(k))));

            Q(ii) = Q(ii) + Vspe(ii)* Vspe(k)*(G(ii,k)*(sin(VolAnгл(ii)-VolAnгл(k))) -
B(ii,k)*(cos(VolAnгл(ii)-VolAnгл(k))));

        end

    end

    % Calculate change from specified value

    dPa = Psp-P;

    dQa = Qsp-Q;

    k = 1;

    dQ = zeros(NumPQ,1);

    for ii = 1:NumberBus

        if BusType(ii) == 3

```

```

    dQ(k,1) = dQa(ii);

    k = k+1;

end

end

dP = dPa(2:NumberBus);

M = [dP; dQ];    % Mismatch Vector

% Jacobian

% J1 - Derivative of Real Power Injections with Angles..

J1 = zeros(NumberBus-1,NumberBus-1);

for ii = 1:(NumberBus-1)

    m = ii+1;

    for k = 1:(NumberBus-1)

        n = k+1;

        if n == m

            for n = 1:NumberBus

                J1(ii,k) = J1(ii,k) + Vspe(m)* Vspe(n)*(-G(m,n)*(sin(VolAngl(m)-
VolAngl(n))) + B(m,n)*(cos(VolAngl(m)-VolAngl(n))));

            end

            J1(ii,k) = J1(ii,k) - Vspe(m)^2*B(m,m);

        else

```

```

        J1(ii,k) = Vspe(m)* Vspe(n)*(G(m,n)*(sin(VolAnгл(m)-VolAnгл(n))) -
B(m,n)*(cos(VolAnгл(m)-VolAnгл(n))));

```

```

    end

```

```

end

```

```

end

```

```

% J2 - Derivative of Real Power Injections with V..

```

```

J2 = zeros(NumberBus-1,NumPQ);

```

```

for ii = 1:(NumberBus-1)

```

```

    m = ii+1;

```

```

    for k = 1:NumPQ

```

```

        n = PQbus(k);

```

```

        if n == m

```

```

            for n = 1:NumberBus

```

```

                J2(ii,k) = J2(ii,k) + Vspe(n)*(G(m,n)*(cos(VolAnгл(m)-VolAnгл(n)))
+ B(m,n)*(sin(VolAnгл(m)-VolAnгл(n))));

```

```

            end

```

```

                J2(ii,k) = J2(ii,k) + Vspe(m)*G(m,m);

```

```

            else

```

```

                J2(ii,k) = Vspe(m)*(G(m,n)*(cos(VolAnгл(m)-VolAnгл(n))) +
B(m,n)*(sin(VolAnгл(m)-VolAnгл(n))));

```

```

            end

```

```

        end

```

```

end

% J3 - Derivative of Reactive Power Injections with Angles..

J3 = zeros(NumPQ,NumberBus-1);

for ii = 1:NumPQ
    m = PQbus(ii);

    for k = 1:(NumberBus-1)
        n = k+1;

        if n == m

            for n = 1:NumberBus

                J3(ii,k) = J3(ii,k) + Vspe(m)* Vspe(n)*(G(m,n)*(cos(VolAnagl(m)-
VolAnagl(n))) + B(m,n)*(sin(VolAnagl(m)-VolAnagl(n))));

            end

            J3(ii,k) = J3(ii,k) - Vspe(m)^2*G(m,m);

        else

            J3(ii,k) = Vspe(m)* Vspe(n)*(-G(m,n)*(cos(VolAnagl(m)-VolAnagl(n))) -
B(m,n)*(sin(VolAnagl(m)-VolAnagl(n))));

        end

    end

end

end

% J4 - Derivative of Reactive Power Injections with V..

```

```

J4 = zeros(NumPQ,NumPQ);
for ii = 1:NumPQ
    m = PQbus(ii);
    for k = 1:NumPQ
        n = PQbus(k);
        if n == m
            for n = 1:NumberBus
                J4(ii,k) = J4(ii,k) + Vspe(n)*(G(m,n)*(sin(VolAnгл(m)-VolAnгл(n))) -
B(m,n)*(cos(VolAnгл(m)-VolAnгл(n))));
            end
            J4(ii,k) = J4(ii,k) - Vspe(m)*B(m,m);
        else
            J4(ii,k) = Vspe(m)*(G(m,n)*(sin(VolAnгл(m)-VolAnгл(n))) -
B(m,n)*(cos(VolAnгл(m)-VolAnгл(n))));
        end
    end
end
end
end
J = [J1 J2; J3 J4];    % Jacobian Matrix..
X = inv(J)*M;         % Correction Vector
dTh = X(1:NumberBus-1);    % Change in Voltage Angle..
dV = X(NumberBus:end);    % Change in Voltage Magnitude.

```

```

% Updating State Vectors..

VolAngl(2:NumberBus) = dTh + VolAngl(2:NumberBus); % Voltage Angle..

k = 1;

for ii = 2:NumberBus

    if BusType(ii) == 3

        Vspe(ii) = dV(k) + Vspe(ii); % Voltage Magnitude..

        k = k+1;

    end

end

Iter = Iter + 1;

Tol = max(abs(M)); % Tolerance..

%disp(Tol)

end

disp(' bus_no mag(V) angle')

disp(' -----')

disp([Bus Vspe VolAngl])

% xlswrite('VOLTAGE.xlsx',V)

%%

V1 = Vspe.*cos(VolAngl)+j*Vspe.*sin(VolAngl);

Vspe=V1;

```

```

%%
SLT = 0;

disp('          Line Flow and Losses \n\n')
disp('  --Line-- Power at bus & line flow  --Line loss-- Transformer\n')
disp('  from to  MW   Mvar   MVA   MW   Mvar   tap\n')
disp('  -----')
)

for n = 1:NumberBus
    busprt = 0;
    for L = 1:NumberBranch;
        if busprt == 0

            busprt = 1;
        else
            end
        if send(L)==n
            k = receive(L);
            In = (Vspe(n) - a(L)*Vspe(k))*y(L)/a(L)^2 + LineCharge(L)/a(L)^2*Vspe(n);
            Ik = (Vspe(k) - Vspe(n)/a(L))*y(L) + LineCharge(L)*Vspe(k);

```

```

Snk = Vspe(n)*conj(In)*MVAb;
Skn = Vspe(k)*conj(Ik)*MVAb;
SL = Snk + Skn;
SLT = SLT + SL;

end

if send(L)==n || receive(L)==n
    fprintf('%12g', k),
    fprintf('%9.3f', real(Snk)), fprintf('%9.3f', imag(Snk))
    fprintf('%9.3f', abs(Snk)),
    fprintf('%9.3f', real(SL)),
        if send(L) ==n && a(L) ~= 1
            fprintf('%9.3f', imag(SL)), fprintf('%9.3f\n', a(L))
        else
            fprintf('%9.3f\n', imag(SL))
        end
    end
else
end

end

end

```

```

%SLT = SLT/2;

fprintf(' \n'), fprintf(' Total loss in ')

fprintf('%9.3fMW', real(SLT)), fprintf('%9.3fMVAr \n', imag(SLT));

%converted into KVAb

fprintf('TOTAL REAL POWER LOSS = %6.4fkW.\n',real(SLT)*1000);

fprintf('TOTAL REACTIVE POWER LOSS = %6.4fkVAr.\n',imag(SLT)*1000);

Ppu=real(SLT)/MVA; %real power loss in per unit

Qpu=imag(SLT)/MVA; %reactive power loss in per unit

VDD=abs(ones(112,1)-abs(Vspe));

cvd=sum(abs(ones(112,1)-abs(Vspe)));%cumulative voltage divation

wp=0.5; %weight of real power loss

wq=0.4; %weight of reactive power loss

wv=0.1; %weight cumulative voltage deviation

ff=wp*Ppu+wq*Qpu+wv*cvd%defining the fitness function

%%%find minimum voltage

% xlswrite('TOTAL REAL POWER LOSS.xlsx',real(SLT)*1000)

% xlswrite('TOTAL REACTIVE POWER LOSS.xlsx',imag(SLT)*1000)

V_min=min(abs(Vspe));

flag=0;

n=1;

while n<=NumberBus

```

```
if V_min==abs(Vspe(n))
    disp('Minimum Voltage appearing at bus')
    disp(n)
    disp('Value of Minimum Voltage')
    disp(V_min)
    flag=1;
end
if flag==1
    n=NumberBus;
end
n=n+1;
end
```

Appendix-B2: Sub Program for Loss Sensitivity

```
ZZ= bus112();

%determining Zbus impedance matrix

for ii=1:112

    for jj=1:112

        alfa(ii,jj)=real(ZZ(ii,jj))*cos(angle(Vspe(ii))-
angle(Vspe(jj)))/(abs(Vspe(ii))*abs(Vspe(jj)));%loss coefficients

        beta(ii,jj)=real(ZZ(ii,jj))*sin(angle(Bus(ii))-
angle(Vspe(jj)))/(abs(Vspe(ii))*abs(Vspe(jj)));%loss coefficients

    end

end

p=BusData(:,7);
q=BusData(:,8);

lsf=zeros(112,1);%initializing loss sensitivity factor

for ii=1:112

    for jj=1:112

        lsf(ii)=lsf(ii)+2*(alfa(ii,jj)*p(jj)-beta(ii,jj)*q(jj));%loss sensitivity factors for
each buses

    end

end

lsf(:,2)=[1:112]'
```

```
loss_sensitivity=sortrows(lsf,-1)%sorting loss sensitivity factors for each nodes in ascending order
```

```
BusData=xlsread('LOSS_SENSITIVITY.xlsx');
```

```
switch 3
```

```
case 1
```

```
N=stem(S(:,2),S(:,1)*1e4,'-ob')%z(:,3))
```

```
legend('Loss Sensitivity Without DG','FontSize',18)
```

```
% ylim ([0 70000])
```

```
% legend('Without DG','FontSize',18)
```

```
case 2
```

```
N=stem(S(:,4),S(:,3)*1e4,'-ob')
```

```
legend('Loss Sensitivity With One DG','FontSize',18)
```

```
ylim ([0 1.8*1e1000000])
```

```
case 3
```

```
N=stem(S(:,6),S(:,5)*1e3,'-ob')
```

```
legend('Loss Sensitivity With Two DG','FontSize',18)
```

```
ylim ([0 12000])
```

```
case 4
```

```
N=stem(S(:,8),S(:,7)*1e4,'-ob')
```

```
ylim ([0 15000])
```

```
legend('Loss Sensitivity With Three DG','FontSize',18)
```

```

case 5
    N=stem(S(:,10),S(:,9)*1e3,'-ob')
ylim ([0 12000])
legend('Loss Sensitivity With one DG','FontSize',18)
case 6
    N=stem(S(:,12),S(:,11)*1e3,'-ob')
ylim ([0 10000])
legend('Loss Sensitivity With Two DG','FontSize',18)
case 7
    N=stem(S(:,14),S(:,13)*1e3,'-ob')
ylim ([0 10000])
legend('Loss Sensitivity With Three DG','FontSize',18)
end
ts=sprintf('Loss Sensitivity at all nodes','FontSize',18)
title(ts,'FontSize',18)
% ylim ([0 1.5])
xlim ([0 112])
xlabel('Bus Number','FontSize',18);
ylabel('Loss Sensitivity','FontSize',18);
% legend('Loss Sensitivity','FontSize',18)
set(findall(gcf,'Type','line'),'LineWidth',1.5)

```

```
set(gca,'FontSize',18)
set(gca,'LineWidth',1.5)
% grid on
cc=abs(Vspe);
[cc [1:112]]
disp(cvd)
disp(ff)
```

Appendix-B3: Sub program for Zbus formation

```
Z=0.0392 + 0.0412i ;
for k1=1:111
    p=B(k1,1);
    q=B(k1,2);
    z=B(k1,3);
    k=B(k1,4);
    if k==1
        Z=add_tree(Z,p,q,z);
    else
        Z=add_chain(Z,p,q,z);
    end
end
end
```

```
disp('impedance=');  
% disp(Z);  
ZZ=Z;  
xlswrite('ZBUSOF112.xlsx',Z);
```

Appendix-B4: Sub Program for Genetic Algorithm

```
% ObjectiveFunction = @mekelle112bus(x);
```

```
busd=xlsread('Busdata12.xlsx');
```

```
switch 2
```

```
    case 1
```

```
nvars = 1; % Number of variables
```

```
P_Ulimit=0.75*sum(busd(:,7));
```

```
P_Llimit=0.25*sum(busd(:,7));
```

```
Q_Ulimit=0.75*sum(busd(:,8));
```

```
Q_Llimit=0.25*sum(busd(:,8));
```

```
LB = [0]; % Lower bound
```

```
UB = [P_Ulimit];
```

```
A=[1;-1];
```

```
B=[P_Ulimit;P_Llimit];
```

```
    case 2
```

```
nvars = 2; % Number of variables
```

```
P_Ulimit=0.75*sum(busd(:,7));
```

```
P_Llimit=0.25*sum(busd(:,7));
```

```
Q_Ulimit=0.75*sum(busd(:,8));
```

```
Q_Llimit=0.25*sum(busd(:,8));
```

```

LB = [0 0 ]; % Lower bound
UB = [P_Ulimit P_Ulimit ];
A=[1 1;-1 -1 ];% Upper bound
B=[P_Ulimit;-P_Llimit ];

case 3

nvars = 3; % Number of variables
P_Ulimit=0.75*sum(busd(:,7));
P_Llimit=0.25*sum(busd(:,7));
Q_Ulimit=0.75*sum(busd(:,8));
Q_Llimit=0.25*sum(busd(:,8));
LB = [0 0 0]; % Lower bound
UB = [P_Ulimit P_Ulimit P_Ulimit];
A=[1 1 1 ;-1 -1 -1];% Upper bound
B=[P_Ulimit;-P_Llimit];

end

options = gaoptimset;

% Modify options setting
% options = gaoptimset(options,'PopInitRange',[0 0 0 ;P_Ulimit P_Ulimit
P_Ulimit ]);
% options = gaoptimset(options,'InitialPopulation',[P_Ulimit P_Ulimit P_Ulimit]);

```

`% options = gaoptimset(options,'InitialScores' , 10); % is initial Total congestion
in test system`

`options = gaoptimset(options,'CrossoverFraction' ,0.85);`

`options = gaoptimset(options,'PopulationSize' ,200);`

`options = gaoptimset(options,'Generations' ,200);`

`options = gaoptimset(options,'SelectionFcn' ,@selectionroulette);`

`options = gaoptimset(options,'CrossoverFcn' ,@crossovertwopoint);`

`options = gaoptimset(options,'MutationFcn' ,@mutationadaptfeasible);`

`%options = gaoptimset(options,'StallGenLimit' ,1);`

`%options = gaoptimset(options,'TimeLimit' ,1000);`

`%options = gaoptimset(options,'StallTimeLimit',1);`

`%options = gaoptimset(options,'TolFun' ,1e-1);`

`%options = gaoptimset(options,'TolCon' ,1e-1);`

`options = gaoptimset(options,'Display' ,'iter');`

`options = gaoptimset(options,'PlotFcns',{ @ gaplotbestf @gaplotbestindiv...`

`@gaplotdistance ...`

`@gaplotexpectation @gaplotgenealogy ...`

`@gaplotrange @gaplotscorediversity @gaplotscores ...`

`@gaplotselection @gaplotstopping @gaplotmaxconstr});`

```

[x,fval,exitflag,output,population] =
ga(@mekelle112bus,nvars,A,B,[],[],LB,UB,[],options);
%  xlswrite('mekelle112bus.xlsx',mekelle112bus)

switch 5

case 1

    x=[x(1)];

    disp('Active Capacity of DG 1:')

    disp(x(1))

case 2

    x=[x(1) x(2) ];

    disp('Active Capacity of DG 1:')

    disp(x(1))

    disp('Active Capacity of DG 2:')

    disp(x(2))

case 3

    x=[x(1) x(2) x(3)];

    disp('Active Capacity of DG 1:')

    disp(x(1))

    disp('Active Capacity of DG 2:')

    disp(x(2))

    disp('Active Capacity of DG 3:')

```

```

disp(x(3))
case 4
x=[x(1)];
pf=0.85;
d=acosd(pf);
c=tand(d);
x(2)=c*x(1);
disp('Active Capacity of DG 1:')
disp(x(1))
disp('Reactive Capacity of DG 1:')
disp(x(2))
case 5
x=[x(1) x(2) ];%x(3) x(4)];
pf=0.85
d=acosd(pf)
c=tand(d)
x(3)=c*x(1)
x(4)=c*x(2)
disp('Active Capacity of DG 1:')
disp(x(1))
disp('Reactive Capacity of DG 1:')

```

```

disp(x(3))

disp('Active Capacity of DG 2:')

disp(x(2))

disp('Reactive Capacity of DG 2:')

disp(x(4))

case 6

x=[x(1) x(2) x(3)];

pf=0.85;

d=acosd(pf);

c=tand(d);

x(4)=c*x(1);

x(5)=c*x(2);

x(6) =c*x(3) ;

disp('Active Capacity of DG 1:')

disp(x(1))

disp('Reactive Capacity of DG 1:')

disp(x(4))

disp('Active Capacity of DG 2:')

disp(x(2))

disp('Reactive Capacity of DG 2:')

disp(x(5))

```

```
disp('Active Capacity of DG 3:')  
disp(x(3))  
disp('Reactive Capacity of DG 3:')  
disp(x(6))  
end
```